

Deliverable 1.2

European ecosystem and market opportunities assessment

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Acronyms and Definitions

Acronyms	Defined as
ADAS	Advanced driver-assistance systems
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet of Things
AIPPS	ARTEMIS Innovation Pilot Projects
ALD	Atomic Layer Deposition
AMP	American Maritime Partnership
ARPA-E	Advanced Research Projects Agency–Energy
ARRA	American Recovery and Reinvestment Act
ARTEMIS-IA	Advanced Research and Technology for Embedded Intelligence and Systems Industry Association
ASICs	Application-specific integrated circuit
ATM	Air Traffic Management
CMOS	Complementary metal–oxide–semiconductor
CMS	Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services
CPS	Cyber-Physical Systems
CPSoS	Cyber-Physical Systems of Systems
CPS PWG	Cyber-Physical Systems Public Working Group
CRM	Customer relationship management
CRYSTAL	CRITICAL sYSTEM engineering AccELeration project
CSA	Coordination and Support Actions
DHS	Department of Homeland Security
DOE	Department of Energy
DOT	Department of Transportation
EASA	European Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission

ECSEL	Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership
ECSEL-JU	Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership programme
EISA	Energy Independence and Security Act of 2007
EMC	ElectroMagnetic Compatibility
ERP	Enterprise resource planning
ESA	Energy Storage Association
ESOs	European Standards Organizations
EU	European Union
EUV	Extreme ultraviolet lithography
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
FAST Act	Fixing America's Surface Transportation Act
FHA	Federal Health Architecture
GDP	Gross domestic product
HMIs	Human-machine interface
HPC	High Performance Computing
ICT	Information and communications technology
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IERC	IoT European Research Cluster
IIC	Industrial Internet Consortium
IODP	Integrated and Open Development Platform
IoT	Internet of Things
ISGAN	International Smart Grid Action Network
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
ITA	International Trade Administration
ITL	Information Technology Laboratory
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ITS JPO	ITS Joint Program Office
I4MS	Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs Initiative
LED	Light Emitting Diodes
LI	Large Industry
MEMS	Microelectromechanical systems
MMICs	Millimetre Wave Integrated Circuits
NAS	National Airspace System
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NCATS	National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences
NCI	National Cancer Institute
NFC	Near Field Communication
NIBIB	National Institute of Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering
NIH	National Institutes of Health
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
NITRD	Networking and Information Technology Research and Development
NSF	National Science Foundation
NSTC	National Science and Technology Council
OCF	Open Connectively Foundation
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OIC	Open Interconnect Consortium
OLEDs	Organic light-emitting diode
OMG	Object Management Group
PJM	Pennsylvania-New Jersey-Maryland Interconnection (regional transmission organization in the United States)
PMA	Premarket approval
PMP	Prodrive Motion Platform
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
PV	Photovoltaics
RF	Radio frequency

RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RTOs	Research Technology Organisations
RTP	Reference Technology Platform
RUS	Department of Agriculture's Rural Utilities Service
SAE	Smart Anything Anywhere
SDD	Silicon Drift Detectors
SGA	Smart Growth America
SGCC	Cyber-security Committee
SGDP	Smart Grid Demonstration Program
SGIG	Smart Grid Investment Grant Program
SGIP	Smart Grid Interoperability Panel
SIPM	Silicon Photomultipliers
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SoS	System of systems
SRA	Strategic Research Agenda
SSI	Smart Systems Integration
SSTI	State Smart Transportation Initiative
SysML	Systems Modeling Language
TIFIA	Transportation Infrastructure Finance and Innovation Act
TRL	Technology readiness levels
TT-NOC	Time-triggered support for multi-core chips
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
US	United States of America
USDA-NIFA	U.S. Department of Agriculture-National Institute of Food and Agriculture
USV	Unmanned surface vehicle
UUV	Unmanned underwater vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
XUV	Solar soft X-ray
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
5G	Fifth Generation

Executive Summary

This document presents an analysis of the European ecosystem that supports the area of CPS and also provides a market opportunities assessment particularly with respect to entry into US markets.

Figure 1. Overview of Deliverable Contents

The report begins by providing an overview of the European landscape (See top half of Figure 1) that supports the CPS domain, covering a range of EU programmes, Industrial Associations, PPPs and supporting technology hubs. A survey of European technology providers has been performed (with a focus on Large Industry and SMEs) to identify stakeholders in the CPS ecosystem. This has identified the technologies being provided or currently under development, the targeted application domains, existing industrial alliances, and standards being supported or developed. This was done by surveying existing lists of technology providers actively engaged in CPS projects. Based on the outcomes of previous work considering worldwide market segmentation [1], market figures and competition analysis, opportunities for European stakeholders were then identified along with roadblocks.

The US market offers significant opportunities for European companies and there are major developments underway. However, US companies provide stiff competition in the CPS/IoT sector and currently dominate the area of platforms and the Internet. The report thus considers the current US orientations and support for the CPS/IoT domain (See lower half of Figure 1) using public information complemented by interviews and input from key US proponents such as NIST and NSF. This identified a number of technical areas where there are opportunities for European companies. The business opportunities in the US transportation, energy, manufacturing, health and wellbeing sectors are then considered also identifying entry barriers/roadblocks for European companies. Success stories of European technologies being exploited in the US were sought to identify lessons learnt that can be used to further the success of the European CPS and IoT industry. The report identifies common pitfalls and provides advice on the keys to success of taking European technologies to the US market considering, in particular, the challenges that face smaller companies.

1 Introduction

The term Cyber-Physical System (CPS) describes hardware-software system, which tightly couple the physical and the virtual world. They are established by networking embedded systems, utilising connections with the outside world through sensors and actuators. They have the capability to collaborate, adapt, and evolve. Support for development and integration of Cyber-Physical Systems is seen as essential for the future as there will be an increasing number of interacting systems with strong connectivity utilised in both society and in industry.

Cyber-Physical Systems find their application in many highly relevant areas to our society: multi-modal transport, eHealth, smart factories, smart grids and smart cities among others. The deployment of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) is expected to increase substantially over the next decades, holding great potential for novel applications and innovative product development. However, the inherent complexity of CPSs, as well as the need to meet optimised performance and comply with essential requirements like safety, security and privacy, raises many questions that still need to be explored by the research community.

Figure 2. Overview of the Platforms4CPS Objectives

The Platforms4CPS consortium aims to “create the vision, strategy, technology building blocks and supporting ecosystem for future CPS applications” as shown in Figure 2 with three key objectives to:

- Create a vision and strategy for future European CPS by analysing the ecosystem and market perspective and strategically updating and validating existing CPS roadmaps across multiple domains
- Promote platform building, bringing together industry and academic experts and create a repository of CPS technology building blocks
- Build an ecosystem by creating a constituency and through cooperating with ECSEL, ITEA, and ARTEMIS projects on the foundations of CPS engineering, and consensus building on societal and legal issues related to the deployment of CPS.

As part of this work this report builds upon previous work on a market analysis for CPS [1] considering the European Ecosystem in CPS, identifying stakeholders and also market opportunities

for the community. The report is divided into sections. The report begins by providing an overview of the European landscape that supports the CPS domain. Technology providers who are stakeholders in the ecosystem and are active in CPS projects are then identified. An aim here was to establish the technologies being provided or currently under development, the targeted application domains, existing industrial alliances, and standards being supported or developed. Based on the outcomes of work on worldwide market segmentation, market figures and competition analysis, opportunities for European stakeholders are then identified along with roadblocks that need addressing.

There is considerable world-wide competition in the sector and a major opportunity for European companies is in the US. Platforms4CPS, in particular, targets the transport, manufacturing, energy and health sectors and a key aim of this report is to assess the competition, roadblocks and opportunities for European companies in these areas within the US market. The report thus considers the current US orientations and support for the CPS/IoT domain in these areas. In this respect developments and initiatives in the US have been considered to understand where there may be synergies and opportunities for European companies. Barriers and roadblocks have also been considered both in terms of the technologies and also with respect to entering the US market. Finally, in section 6.9 the report considers success stories of European technologies being exploited in the US to identify lessons learnt. Common pitfalls are identified which are particularly relevant to SMEs and advice is provided on how to successfully bring European technologies to the US market.

2 European Supporting Ecosystem

Figure 3. M2M World of Connected Services (Source Cisco)

Within Europe, support for development and integration of Cyber-Physical Systems and the Internet of Things is seen as essential for the future. As the embedded world meets the Internet world there will be an increasing number of interacting systems with strong connectivity utilised in both society and in industry (See Figure 3). Connectivity between embedded systems and computing devices is predicted to grow massively over the coming years. Gartner [2] for instance, estimates that there will be 26 billion connected devices (excluding PCs, tablets and smartphones) by 2020 world-wide, and

even higher predictions of 40-50 billion devices are being made by other analyst companies. This equates to a global market value of \$1.9 trillion, of which 80% is expected to come from services. Europe is a world leader in the area of time-critical and safety-critical systems and to maintain this position there is a need to be able to design, develop and deploy highly distributed and connected digital technologies [3]. Underlying this is a need for the development and introduction of platforms for CPS deployment. This is seen as key to the future competitiveness but only through building a supporting ecosystem of developers and users can a platform flourish and become successful. Europe has a strong position in ICT market with an ecosystem of world leading suppliers and systems integrators. The embedded systems industry alone creates 50,000 new jobs every year and Europe accounts for 34% of world production of embedded systems with particular strengths in the automotive sector, aerospace and health [3].

CPS/IoT/digitalisation is expected to change our everyday lives and open up new business opportunities to provide:

- efficient, environmentally friendly, autonomous and safe mobility in the automotive, aeronautics, rail, maritime and logistics sectors
- greater efficiency in management and operations for process automation, manufacturing, conventional/renewable power plants, energy conversion, smart grids and smart metering
- greater benefits to citizens via smart, safe and secure cities, energy efficient buildings and green infrastructure (traffic management, lighting, water and waste management)
- smart devices and services for smart home functionality, home monitoring, health services and assisted living.

To support this European Commissioner Gunther Oettinger in his speech on “A Digital Single Market Strategy”, highlighted the need for Industrial Leadership in the Digital Economy. The second key pillar of this strategy is to create leadership in platforms for digital industry with the objective to “ensure the availability of state-of-the-art open and interoperable platforms that any business can use to make its products, processes or services ready for the digital age”. The development of such platforms requires collaboration between actors across value chains, including users and the supply industry so it is necessary to bring these together. To achieve this the ECSEL Joint Technology Initiative and PPPs in Factories of the Future, 5G and Big Data were set up and it is planned to launch at least 5 large-scale platform projects per year until 2018. Investment in platform-building in Horizon 2020 is expected to reach more than €800 million in the next five years with matching investment from industry and government of €3 billion until 2020. To build the Digital Single Market it is also necessary to address the skills gap and legal issues. Collaboration and consensus building on standards and platforms for strategic positioning of European industry is required as it is essential to have common standards and interoperable solutions throughout the products and services life cycles.

Within the European Union the idea of “Smart Everything Everywhere” is very much a key concept that is being promoted for the future to highlight the importance of ubiquitous “smartness”. The majority of IoT research and development to date has focused on sensors and on providing connectivity, whereas the real value to users and society is from using the information provided by the sensors and networks in a smart fashion (and in connecting sensing to actuation to create a CPS). Connectivity from the Internet of Things is thus seen as an enabling technology for Cyber-Physical Systems that close the loop from sensors to actually influence users and physical systems. The enormous potential of these technologies has been recognised by the European Union, as CPS and IoT are key pillars of the Europe 2020 initiative Digital Agenda for Europe [4] and of other research and innovation programmes, e.g. the ECSEL Joint Undertaking, EUREKA/ITEA, and the ARTEMIS Industry Association. Cyber-Physical Systems are seen as an important area for Europe with a potential 410B€ market, 4 million associated jobs worldwide of which one quarter are in Europe [2]. The area is expected to contribute to employment, quality of life and industrial competitiveness across all sectors.

A major initiative launched in April 2016 is the Digitising European Industry initiative [5]. This aims to link national initiatives for the digitisation of industry and related services and to boost investment through strategic partnerships and networks. Although many areas within Europe have embraced the take up digital technologies and processes some sectors are lagging behind such as construction, agro-food, textiles and steel. It is estimated that digitisation of products and services will add more than €110 billion of revenue for industry per year in Europe in the next five years [5]. To support this several EU Member States have launched strategies to support the digitisation of industry, however, the aim of the Commission is to coordinate activities across Europe to avoid fragmentation. Key areas being addressed are standards for 5G, Cloud computing, Internet of Things, data technologies and cyber-security. The Commission will also set up a European Cloud to give Europe's 1.7 million researchers and 70 million science and technology professionals a virtual environment to store, manage, analyse and re-use a big amount of research data. The Commission [5] intends to:

- help coordinate national and regional initiatives on digitising industry
- focus investments in EU's public-private partnerships
- invest €500 million in a pan-EU network of digital innovation hubs (centres of excellence in technology) where businesses can obtain advice and test digital innovations.
- set up large-scale pilot projects to strengthen Internet of Things, advanced manufacturing and technologies in smart cities and homes, connected cars or mobile health services.
- adopt future-proof legislation that will support the free flow of data and clarify ownership of data generated by sensors and smart devices. The Commission will also review rules on safety and liability of autonomous systems.
- present an EU skills agenda that will help give people the skills needed for jobs in the digital age.

It is expected that €50 billion of public and private investments will be mobilised in support of the digitisation of industry. In order to create critical mass the Commission has an approach of “clustering” projects in key areas. In the following sections key clusters and projects are highlighted in the areas of CPS and also IoT.

2.1 European H2020 Cluster of CPS Projects

In the CPS Cluster of projects the EC funded 11 Research and Innovation Actions, 4 Innovation Actions and 4 Coordination and Support Actions under H2020 to provide coverage across a number of areas. The latest round of funding supported the Platforms4CPS Coordination and Support Action, and the DEIS, CERBERO and CPSwarm Research and Innovation Actions. The Research and Innovation Actions are addressing areas such as co-simulation/modelling of all of system levels, including circuits, communication networks, firmware, operating system, system architecture and software layers with a view to providing model-based design. The aim is to reduce development cost and time by managing and reducing complexity. There are a broad range of use cases and the projects support more fundamental and longer term research. The different projects and their coverage are briefly outlined below.

Research and Innovation Actions

- TAPPS: Trusted Apps for open CPS developing a platform for open CPS Apps with high security standards
- SAFURE: SAFety and secURity by design for interconnected mixed-critical Cyber-Physical Systems providing safety and security by construction for mixed-critical systems at design and run-time

- UnCoVerCPS: Unifying Control and Verification of Cyber-Physical Systems within the tool chain through modelling, verification, conformance testing and code generation
- U-TEST: Testing Cyber-Physical Systems under Uncertainty by developing systematic, extensible, and configurable model-based and search-based testing methodologies for building dependable CPS, and testing for uncertainty
- AXIOM: Agile, eXtensible, fast I/O Module to allow easy programmability of multi-core multiboard systems
- IMMORTAL: Integrated Modelling, Fault Management, Verification and Reliable Design Environment for Cyber-Physical Systems addressing reliable design and real time fault management in multi-core CPS
- INTO-CPS: INtegrated TOol chain for model-based design of CPSs providing an integrated tool chain for comprehensive model-based design of CPS
- COSSIM: A Novel, Comprehensible, Ultra-Fast, Security-Aware CPS Simulator providing an open-source framework to simulate the networking and processing parts of a CPS more accurately, more quickly and while considering security
- DEIS: Dependable system integration based on Digital Dependability Identities (DDI's) for automotive, rail and healthcare applications.
- CPSwarm: Proposing a new science of system integration and tools to support engineering of CPS swarms to ease development and integration of complex herds of heterogeneous CPS that collaborate and exhibit a collective behaviour to solve complex, industrial-driven problems.
- CERBERO: Cross-layer modElbased fRamework for multi-oBjective dEsign of Reconfigurable systems in uncertain hybrid enviroNments.
- BONSEYES: Developing a platform consisting of a Data Marketplace, Deep Learning Toolbox, and Developer Reference Platforms for organizations wanting to adopt Artificial Intelligence in low power IoT devices ("edge computing"), embedded computing systems, or data centre servers ("cloud computing").

Innovation Actions

In addition to the already running EUROCPs and CPSELabs which are described later two further projects are being funded:

- EOT: Eyes of Things building an ultra-low power and low cost vision platform for surveillance, augmented reality/wearable, cloud computing and perceptual computing
- CP-SETIS: Towards Cyber-Physical Systems Engineering Tools Interoperability Standardisation to produce an International Open Standard for development tools

Coordination and Support Actions

A number of Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) have been funded in the CPS area. These have addressed the development of strategic roadmaps for CPS and EU-US collaboration.

- Road2CPS: Strategic action for future CPS through roadmaps, impact multiplication and constituency building
- TAMS4CPS: Trans-Atlantic Modelling and Simulation For Cyber-Physical Systems
- CPS-SUMMIT: Bringing experts together to identify research areas where the EU and US may work together, e.g. trustworthy systems
- Platforms4CPS: to 'create the vision, strategy, technology building blocks and supporting ecosystem for future CPS applications'

2.2 European Cluster of CPSoS Projects

Figure 4. European Cluster of CPSoS Projects

Previously under FP7 and H2020 the European Commission has also funded a number of Integrated Projects and Research and Innovation Projects to create a cluster of Cyber-Physical Systems of Systems projects (CPSoS). These are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 5. DANSE and COMPASS Integrated Projects

Within this cluster two large Integrated projects (See Figure 5) were funded DANSE (Designing for Adaptation and evolution in System of systems Engineering) which addressed approaches for SoS engineering considering the need to deal with an evolving, adaptive and iterative life cycle, and COMPASS (Comprehensive Modelling for Advanced System of Systems) which addressed model-based techniques for developing and maintaining Systems of Systems based on augmenting SysML with CML supported by proof and model checking tools. These projects addressed a diverse number of applications, including aerospace, autonomous vehicles, water management, emergency management and audio/video/home automation.

Other smaller projects within the cluster are:

- AMADEOS: Architecture for Multi-criticality Agile Dependable Evolutionary Open System-of-Systems
- AGILE: RAPidly-deployable, self-tuninG, self-reconfigurabLE, nearly-optimal control design for large-scale nonlinear systems for Urban Traffic Control (UTC) targeting a road network of Chania, Greece, and control of an Office Building
- LOCAL4GLOBAL: System-of-Systems that act LOCALly For optimising GLOBALLY to create a plug-and-play control mechanism for the constituent systems of a SoS
- DYMASOS: Dynamic Management of Physically Coupled Systems of Systems addressing the management of large physically coupled systems of systems.

A number of roadmapping activities were also funded:

- CyPhERS: Cyber-Physical European Roadmap. The CyPhERS project developed a European strategic research and innovation agenda for Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) identifying and prioritising research areas, support measures for both horizontal and vertical cooperation, research funding policies, training and standardization.
- ROAD2SOS: A Roadmap for Innovation in SoS. The project defined roadmaps for the domains of distributed energy generation and smart grids, integrated multi-site industrial production, emergency and crisis management, and multi-modal traffic control.
- T-AreaSoS: Trans-Atlantic Research and Education Agenda on Systems of Systems with the aim to create a commonly agreed EU-US Systems of Systems (SoS) research agenda.
- CPSoS: Cyber-Physical Systems of Systems. CPSoS provided a forum and an exchange platform for systems of systems related communities/projects and also produced a strategic research and innovation agenda.

With respect to Platforms4CPS the CyPhERS and CPSoS projects are particularly relevant as they covered smart cities, smart transportation and smart energy.

2.3 Factories of the Future Cluster

Manufacturing is a key domain in Europe where CPS is being exploited. A number of projects have been funded in the area under FP7 and Horizon 2020. Currently there are 11 projects in the Factories of the Future Cluster. These are:

- AUTOWARE: Wireless Autonomous, Reliable and Resilient Production Operation Architecture for Cognitive Manufacturing which is creating a reference architecture (aligned with CRYSTAL and EMC2 CPS design practices and ARROWHEAD cloudification approach - see section 2.5.1).
- DAEDALUS: Distributed control and simulAtion platform to support an Ecosystem of DigitAl aUtomation developerS utilising virtualised intelligence and a distributed automation platform based on IEC-61499 standard.
- DISRUPT: Decentralised architectures for optimised operations via virtualised processes and manufacturing ecosystem collaboration for flexible factories that can be quickly reprogrammed to provide faster time-to-market and meet mass-customisation needs.
- FAR-EDGE Factory Automation Edge Computing Operating System Reference Implementation based on RAMI 4.0 providing an automation platform based on edge computing architectures and IoT/CPS technologies thereby creating an ecosystem for FI factory automation solutions.

- SAFIRE: Cloud-based Situational Analysis for Factories providing Real-time Reconfiguration Services to enable “Reconfiguration as a Service” for dynamic smart factory systems using cloud-based services and computing power.
- ScalABLE4.0: Scalable automation for flexible production systems to demonstrate an open scalable production system framework (OSPS) that can be used efficiently and effectively to visualize, virtualize, construct, control, maintain and optimize production lines.
- COMPOSITION: Developing an ecosystem for collaborative manufacturing processes for both intra- and interfactory integration and automation based on a digital automation framework providing multi-level, real-time cross-domain analytics and decision support.
- DIGICOR: Decentralised Agile Coordination Across Supply Chains addressing the development of a collaboration platform, tools, and services for the setup and coordination of production networks of SMEs and logistics providers in the supply chain.
- NIMBLE: Collaboration Network for Industry, Manufacturing, Business and Logistics in Europe developing the infrastructure for a cloud-based, Industrie 4.0, Internet-of-things-enabled B2B platform for European manufacturing firms.
- vf-OS: Producing a Virtual Factory Open Operating System and Software Development Kit (OAK) for Factories of the Future that aims to be the reference system software for collaborative manufacturing and logistics processes supported by a multi-sided application marketplace and development studio.
- ConnectedFactories a Coordination and Support Action CSA considering industrial scenarios for Connected Factories, identifying upcoming technological approaches and best practices, future needs and challenges, and platforms for digital integration and interoperability of manufacturing systems and processes.

2.4 EIT Digital

EIT Digital [6] is a European digital innovation and entrepreneurial education organisation which has the aim of driving Europe’s digital transformation. It brings together 130 top European corporations, SMEs, start-ups, universities and research institutes. It is focused on entrepreneurship and targets the integration of education, research and business by bringing together students, researchers, engineers, business developers and entrepreneurs. This is done in a network of centres located in Berlin, Eindhoven, Helsinki, London, Paris, Stockholm, Trento, Budapest, Madrid and also Silicon Valley. Strategically EIT Digital addresses the market uptake of research-based digital technologies focusing on Europe’s strategic, societal challenges: Digital Industry, Digital Cities, Digital Wellbeing and Digital Infrastructure.

2.5 ARTEMIS-IA

Figure 6. ARTEMIS Strategic Roadmap

Industry across Europe has also joined forces to address the area of CPS. The ARTEMIS Industry Association (Advanced Research and Technology for Embedded Intelligence and Systems) [7] is an association of European actors in Embedded & Cyber-Physical Systems. ARTEMIS represents its members (industry, SMEs, universities and research institutes) coordinating strategy and promoting R&I interests to the European Commission and the Public Authorities of the participating states. The Industry Association follows on from the ARTEMIS European Technology Platform and maintains responsibility for the ARTEMIS Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) on Embedded & Cyber-Physical Systems (See Figure 6). There are more than 180 members and associates from all over Europe with a wide range of backgrounds and disciplines being represented.

In conjunction with the European Union and Member States the ARTEMIS JU was set up under FP7 as a tri-partite public private partnership in February 2008 under Council Regulation (EC) No 74/2008 of 20 December 2007 [8] as a Community body based in Brussels. The aim of the ARTEMIS JU was to implement significant parts of the Strategic Research Agenda put forward [9] by ARTEMIS-IA co-funded by industry, research organisations, participating Member States and the Commission's ICT programme. The ARTEMIS JU was responsible for maintaining the Strategic Research Agenda with the remit to cover embedded systems and tools. The ARTEMIS JU also initiated, managed and co-ordinated research activities through open calls for proposals and via funding research projects. Six calls for projects were made between 2008 and 2013 with total costs of €1.1 billion.

2.5.1 ARTEMIS Project Types

ARTEMIS Sub-programmes (ASPs)	ARTEMIS Innovation Pilot Projects (AIPPs)
ASP1- Methods and processes for safety-relevant embedded systems ASP2- Embedded Systems for Healthcare and Wellbeing ASP3- Embedded Systems in Smart environments ASP4- Embedded systems for manufacturing and process automation ASP5- Computing platforms for embedded systems ASP6- Embedded Systems for Security and Critical Infrastructures Protection ASP7- Embedded Systems supporting sustainable urban life ASP8- Human-centre design of embedded systems	AIPP1- Critical Systems Engineering Factories AIPP2- Innovative Integrated Care Cycles AIPP3- Seamless communication and interoperability - Smart environments: The Neural System for society AIPP4- Production and Energy Systems Automation AIPP5- Computing platforms for embedded systems AIPP6- Intelligent-Built environment and urban infrastructure for sustainable and "friendly" cities

Table 1. ARTEMIS Sub-programmes (ASPs) and Innovation Pilot Projects (AIPPs) (Source: ARTEMIS JU, Annual Activity Report 2013)

Over the period 2008-2013 the ARTEMIS JU launched 6 calls and funded 56 projects engaging 1420 participant entities. There was very good engagement across the embedded systems community driven by end user applications with many projects resulting in demonstrators of technologies at a relatively high TRL. As some applications were safety critical there was also good engagement with public bodies and regulators in some cases.

In later years larger projects were funded. The CRYSTAL project (CRITICAL SYSTEM engineering ACCELERATION) [10], for instance, developed an Interoperability Specification (IOS) and a Reference Technology Platform (RTP) as a European standard for safety-critical systems building upon previous work in iFEST and MBAT. The project had a budget of €82 million with 71 partners from 10 different European countries including OEMs, suppliers, tool vendors and academia. Driven by industry, CRYSTAL aimed to provide a mature, ready-to-use integrated tool chain with TRL of 7. A loose coupling between tools was used to enable sharing and interlinking of data via standardised and open Web technologies. A key aim was to provide common interoperability across various life cycle domains. Real-world industrial use cases from the automotive, aerospace, rail and health sectors were used as a focus for the work.

The EMC² (Embedded Multi-Core Systems for Mixed Criticality Applications in Dynamic and Changeable Real-time Environments) [11] concentrated on computing platforms for embedded systems. The objective of EMC² was to enable the use of multi-core technology across several embedded systems domains. There were 6 Technology Work Packages and a number of Living Labs in the Automotive, Aerospace, Space, Shipping, Railway and Logistics domains. The aim was to allow cost efficient integration of different applications with different levels of safety and security on a single computing platform in an open context. EMC² addressed dynamic adaptability in open systems, handling of mixed-criticality applications under real-time conditions, scalability and flexibility, full-scale deployment and management of integrated tool chains, through the entire lifecycle. The project had 99 industry and research partners from 19 European countries with an effort of around 800 person years and a total budget of about €100 million.

2.6 ECSEL Joint Undertaking

Figure 7. Overview of ECSEL Undertaking

The ECSEL-JU (Electronic Components and Systems for European Leadership) programme [12] was created from a merger of ARTEMIS-JU and the ENIAC-JU in June 2014 and will finish in 2024. ECSEL has coverage from industry in a number of areas including micro-/nanoelectronics, embedded and Cyber-Physical Systems and smart systems as shown in Figure 7. Within the programme projects are funded in several application areas and in key enabling technologies as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. ECSEL Applications and Essential Capabilities

The strategy of ECSEL is decided by a Governing Board which comprises the ARTEMIS Industry Association, AENEAS and EPoSS, participating states and the European Commission. ECSEL makes its own calls to fund R&I projects via the Public Authorities Board. Call topics are agreed by participating states, associated countries and the European Commission. To date six calls have been launched and 39 projects have been selected for funding: 22 Research and Innovation Actions and 17 Innovations Actions. The total funding for these is €1956.8 million with industry providing 56% of this, the remainder being provided by the European Commission and Member States.

2.7 I4MS and Competence Centres

Figure 9. I4MS

The European Commission also identified a need to connect at a regional level with smaller companies. In support of this the I4MS initiative (ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs) was launched in 2013 (See Figure 9) with a budget of €77 million [13]. The aim of the initiative is to help SMEs and mid-caps in the manufacturing sector by providing access to competences that can help in assessing, planning and mastering digital transformation and in providing access to innovation networks and best practice examples. Financial support is also directly provided for digital transformation. Underlying this is the idea to foster collaboration across manufacturing value chains through the help of the competence centres and innovation hubs (HPC centres, universities, application oriented research organisations) across Europe. Short duration experiments are funded to transfer know-how and technology from the innovation hubs to SMEs and mid-caps bridging the competence gap and providing financial means to adopt leading edge technology that can be used to bring innovative new products and services to market. Here cross-border experiments are particularly supported with an intention to broaden the field of the application and open up new markets. Participating competence centres benefit as they extend their research oriented activities with industrial projects.

2.8 SmartAnythingEverywhere

Figure 10. Smart Everything Everywhere Innovation Hubs

Increasingly people are becoming reliant on smart technologies such as smart phones, smart watches and smart TVs and more and more objects are being augmented by digital components hidden inside. For instance, smart offices can turn off the lights when nobody is in the office, or a car can brake automatically when an obstacle is noticed. In support of the Digitisation of European Industry the Smart Anything Anywhere (SAE) [14] initiative has been supported by the European Commission. The aim of this is to build ecosystems based on collaboration between researchers, large industries and SMEs with the aim to transfer knowledge and resources available to a much wider group of companies.

A network of competence centres has been set up (See Figure 10) at research technology organisations (RTOs) or technology transfer-oriented university institutes who cluster technical and application knowledge that supports innovation. The aim is to transfer knowledge and resources available to a much wider group of companies. SMEs who often have great ideas but lack resources, and middle size companies can experiment with new technologies, try them out in their processes and work together with the suppliers of the technology to adapt it to their specific needs. The aim is to help companies innovate their products and services and become more competitive in the global market.

€25 million of funding is being used to support around 100 experiments with the aim of involving more than 200 SMEs and midcaps in the field of Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS), Internet of Things (IoT) and Smart Systems Integration (SSI). Open calls are also made from some of the initiatives within SAE.

- EuroCPS - A network of design centres boosting and initiating synergies between SMEs, major CPS-platforms and competency providers to capture the emerging markets of IoT products. 30 SME led experiments have been initiated.
- CPSELabs – A CPS engineering infrastructure, knowledge and tools for realising novel trustworthy CPS-based products and services. The CPSELabs marketplace provides an open forum for sharing platforms, architectures and SW tools for the engineering of dependable and trustworthy CPS. This innovation initiative funds focused 12-18 month experiments with 2-6 partners.
- Gateone – Is an innovation service for European “smartisation” by SMEs with a focus on bioelectronics technologies. 50 small scale experiments have been funded to deliver innovation concept demonstrators with SMEs engaged in the testing phase.
- Smarter-SI – This initiative provides smart access to manufacturing for systems integration. It utilises a Community Foundry Model (CFM) to accelerate Smart Systems Integration for SMEs to exploit in niche markets (low volume high value) by providing access to design facilities and manufacturing capabilities for prototyping, early validation and first production. A test bed to realise 10 application experiments has been set up.
- Smart4Europe – Smart4Europe will serve the SAE community by bringing together Commission projects aligned to SAE and all parties interested in SAE, with a focus on SMEs and mid-caps. The ultimate goals of Smart4Europe are to reinforce the collaboration between projects supported under SAE increasing their outreach and impact providing wide coverage of stakeholders in technological, application, innovation, and geographic terms.
- FED4SAE – This initiative aims to boost and sustain the digitisation of European Industry by strengthening competitiveness in the CPS Physical Systems (CPS) and embedded system markets. The goal is to create a pan-European network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH) by leveraging existing regional ecosystems bringing together Start-ups SMEs and Midcaps to build new products and services with “digital inside”.
- DIATOMIC – The project aims to establish a sustainable ecosystem to facilitate AME/SSI-based innovation in the health, agri-food and manufacturing sectors, all of which are under-digitised and are of prime importance for society and the economy.
- TETRACOM – The mission of this Coordination Action is to boost European academia-to-industry technology transfer (TT) in all domains of Computing Systems. TETRACOM is a Technology Transfer Project (TTP) with the aim to help to lower the barrier for researchers to make the first steps towards commercialisation of their research results.
- TETRAMAX – The main objective is to address the domain of customized low energy computing (CLEC) for CPS and the IoT. The project will support cross-border Application Experiments and build a new European CLEC competence centre network with the ultimate aim of self-sustainability.
- SMARTEES – SMARTEES is a Digital Innovation Hub dedicated to Organic and Large Area Electronics (OLAE) providing access to competencies and business support for innovation adoption. SMARTEES will provide access to disruptive OLAE technologies and innovation support for their uptake.
- COLAE – The main objective of this Coordination Action is to promote the commercial exploitation of OLAE technology for the benefit of European industry and business. It will provide access to a knowledge base and technology know-how from key European OLAE research partners and their regional OLAE clusters, and provide training and business support.

2.9 Industrie 4.0

Figure 11. Industrie 4.0

A major national initiative in Germany that is addressing the CPS area within manufacturing and automation is Industrie 4.0 [15] (See Figure 11). This is being supported under the German Government's HighTech Strategy 2020 which covers health, nutrition, communication, safety, climate, energy and mobility. There are 10 forward looking projects, two of which are in communications, with €200 million of funding from government. A working group [15] identified 8 action areas: standardisation, reference architecture, mastery of complex systems, national broadband infrastructure, security, organisation and structure, vocational and further education, and legal framework and resource efficiency. The aim is to achieve a quantum leap in organisational management through the entire value chain and product life-cycles. Key technologies identified are dynamic self-organising systems, real-time availability of information, Big Data management and optimisation. An aim is to realise research in the real world and the German BITKOM, VDMA and ZVEI organisations are working together in the Platform Industrie 4.0 initiative. A scientific advisory board has been formed and 4 working groups on strategy, standardisation, research and security have been created. This initiative although driven at a National level in Germany is also driving activities across Europe.

2.10 IOT Initiatives in Europe

Strongly related to the domain of CPS and with significant overlap in many cases the area of IoT is also being supported within Europe by a number of initiatives. In this section a number of key European initiatives are highlighted.

2.10.1 IERC European Research Cluster on the Internet of Things

The IERC (IoT European Research Cluster) [16] is bringing together EU-funded projects with the aim of defining a common vision for IoT technology, identifying research challenges, and coordinating and encouraging the convergence of ongoing work. The cluster includes over 40 European projects including CLOUT, VITAL, SOCIOTAL, RERUM, COSMOS, CITY PULSE, ALMANAC, SMARTIE, SMART-

ACTION, FITMAN, ASPIRE, CASCADAS, CONFIDENCE, CuteLoop, DACAR, EPoSS, EU-IFM, EURIDICE, GRIFS, HYDRA, IMS2020, Indisputable Key, iSURF, LEAPFROG, PEARS Feasibility, PrimeLife, RACE networkRFID, SMART, StoLPaN, SToP, TraSer, WALTER, IOT-A, INTREPID, IOT@Work, ELLIOT, SPRINT, NEFFICS, IOT-I and CASAGRAS2. Clustering of these projects is seen as essential to create a competitive industry and to provide secure, safe and privacy preserving deployment of IoT. Additionally, the IERC also links to Member States’ initiatives and engages with policy activities such as BRIDGE, AITPL, AMI-4-SME, CE-RFID, CoBIS, Dynamite, PRIME, PROMISE and SMMART, and cooperates with other large initiatives such as FIA, 5G, ARTEMIS-IA, AENEAS, EPoSS and the ECSEL JU. Although the IERC has a European aim to enhance Europe's competitiveness and to drive the development of an information based economy and society it also has a global dimension facilitating knowledge sharing at the global, industrial and organisational level to encourage and exchange best practices and new business models that are emerging in different parts of the world. The main objectives of the IERC are to:

- Establish a cooperation platform and develop a research vision for IoT activities in Europe and become a major entry and contact point for IoT research in the world.
- Define an international strategy for cooperation in the area of IoT research and innovation and have an overview of the research and innovation priorities at the global level.
- Coordinate the cooperation activities with other EC Clusters and ICT projects.
- Coordinate and align the SRIA agenda at the European level with the developments at the global level.
- Organise debates/workshops leading to a better understanding of IoT and Future Internet, 5G, cloud technology, and adoption.

2.10.2 AIOTI

Figure 12. AIOTI

The Alliance for the Internet of Things (AIOTI) [17] was launched by the European Commission with key IoT players with the aim of creating a European IoT ecosystem that can promote dialogue and

interaction to give the EU a lead in the technology. The AIOTI is helping the European Commission prepare strategy for future IoT research (See Figure 12) as well as providing input to innovation and standardisation policies. In particular, it provided input to the design of IoT Large Scale Pilots funded under H2020. AIOTI converted to a European association based in Brussels on 22 September 2016.

2.10.3 IOT-EPI Cluster

Figure 13. IOT-EPI Cluster

To support the domain the European Commission has funded the IoT European Platforms Initiative (IoT-EPI) (See Figure 13) which was defined with the help of AIOTI. In the IoT domain there are many platforms that have been developed (over 350) and there is a need for rationalisation. The IoT-EPI is a cluster of research and innovation projects that are working together to deliver an IoT extended into a web of platforms for connected devices and objects. The IoT platforms support smart environments, businesses, services and persons with dynamic and adaptive configuration capabilities. The goal is to overcome the fragmentation of vertically-oriented closed systems, architectures and application areas and move towards open systems and platforms that support multiple applications.

Figure 14. IOT-EPI Task Forces

Within the IoT-EPI a number of task forces have been set up as shown in Figure 14. The aim is to share knowledge, create a brand and jointly plan activities across the cluster enabling more efficient use of resources.

2.11 H2020 IoT Pilot Projects

Within the IoT domain the need for large-scale demonstration of technologies was identified as a key need by both industry and academia. In response the European Commission put out a call with €100 million on Internet of Things Large Scale Pilots [18]. This is aimed at promoting IoT take up in Europe and development of open technologies and platforms to support IoT ecosystems. The Large Scale Pilots are goal driven with the aim of using IoT approaches for real-life industrial/societal challenges. The areas include smart living environments for ageing well, smart farming and food security, wearables for smart ecosystems, reference zones in EU cities and autonomous vehicles in a connected environment. The Large Scale Pilots will involve stakeholders from both the supply and demand side and contain all the technology development, testing, integration and innovation activities for use, application and deployment of IoT. Coordination and support actions are also being funded to encourage cooperation and support cross-fertilisation between pilots and use cases. The pilot areas are:

- Pilot 1: Smart living environments for ageing well (EU contribution up to €20 million)
- Pilot 2: Smart Farming and Food Security (EU contribution up to €30 million)
- Pilot 3: Wearables for smart ecosystems (EU contribution up to €15 million)
- Pilot 4: Reference zones in EU cities (EU contribution up to €15 million)
- Pilot 5: Autonomous vehicles in a connected environment (EU contribution up to €20 million)

International joint IoT calls are also being supported with Japan, South Korea, China and Brazil. A further call will be made in 2017 on sophisticated platform architectures for smart objects, embedded intelligence, and smart networks.

2.12 Platform Building

Figure 15. Platform Building

The EC has announced that 300 MEuros has been allocated in the period 2018-2020 for Platform Building. The key areas identified for funding are:

- Digital Manufacturing Platforms, e.g. Plug and Produce Equipment Platforms
- Agricultural Digital Integration Platforms
- Smart Hospital of the Future & Smart and Healthy Living at Home
- Internet of Things for Energy: Smart Homes and Grids
- 5G for Connected and Automated Driving
- The Construction Sector is also being considered if funding can be found

The expectation is that there will be synergies with other activities under ECSEL, e.g. Lighthouse Projects on Industrie4.E and Mobility4.E as shown in Figure 15. Each project is expected to be large (around 15 MEuros) to encourage European actors to join together to create strategic initiatives. Ideally the projects should pilot applications using existing infrastructure and be leveraged with Industrial and Member State funding by a target factor of 10.

3 Technologies Being Provided and Targeted Application Domains

A survey of European technology providers has been performed to identify stakeholders in the CPS ecosystem. This was done by surveying existing lists of technology providers actively engaged in CPS related projects across Europe. Based on these lists information for each company was gathered via their websites and via their known public activities. This identified the technologies being provided or currently under development, the targeted application domains, and standards/platforms being supported or developed. Notably many companies are engaged in more than one project addressing a range of applications. The survey has concentrated on companies rather than research providers such as RTOs or Universities as the aim of this document is to consider commercial opportunities for companies in the target sectors: transportation, health, manufacturing and energy. The supporting ecosystem of research providers is considered in Section 3.3 considering technology priorities.

In total 217 companies were identified that are active in the CPS domain. The companies were divided into Large Companies and SMEs of which there were 96 and 121 respectively. A full list of companies and the survey analysis is provided in Appendix A (Section 9).

3.1 Survey of Large Companies Engaged in CPS

3.1.1 Sectors Represented by Large Companies

Figure 16. Representation of Sectors by Large Companies

In terms of sectors being addressed by the 96 large companies considered within the survey it is notable that the majority of companies that were surveyed are engaged in manufacturing (35%) (See Figure 16). Transportation is the next most active sector (27%) followed by health (17%). The energy sector is represented by 15% of large companies. In addition to the main categories considered by

Platforms4CPS a number of other sectors were also found. These included construction, water industry, communications, finance, retail, media, gaming and agriculture accounting for around 6% of the total.

3.1.2 Country Representation

Figure 17. Country Representation by Large Company Stakeholders

The distribution of large companies across Europe was also considered, as shown in Figure 17, identifying that German companies are most active in the CPS area at a European level. It is also notable that in the sample used that some countries are currently not represented. This identifies targets for Platforms4CPS activities in the future.

3.1.3 Technology Domains

Semiconductor Manufacturing

- **Raw Materials**, e.g. wafer fabrication equipment and services, natural fused quartz and synthetic fused silica for telecommunications, optical, chemical, and lamp industries.
- **Chip-Making**, e.g. foundry services, lithography, optics, photomask, die attach, bonding and imprint systems, wafer bumping, assembly equipment packaging, plating, Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) thin film coating solutions, roll-to-roll WEB coating, solder ball placement displays, automation equipment and energy management.
- **Metrology**, e.g. equipment for the characterization of semiconductor and photovoltaic materials, for monitoring the manufacturing process of semiconductor devices, flat panel displays and solar cells.
- **Chip and System Design**, e.g. CMOS, RF and ASICs, analog/mixed-signal, semiconductor devices and systems, solutions for automotive, mobility, communications, multimedia, data centres, IoT, RF products and industrial segments.

Sensors

- **Design and Manufacturing**, e.g. silicon-based capacitive sensors for the measurement of acceleration, pressure, inclination, shock, vibration and angular rate, sensors for factory, logistics and process automation, infrared detectors for military, space and commercial applications, leak detectors and plasma sensors, RFID products and IoT solutions, MEMS for consumer, life science, medical, telecom, industrial and automotive applications, sensor ICs,

interfaces and related software for consumer, communications, industrial, medical, and automotive markets.

Actuation

- **Design and Manufacturing**, e.g. advanced motion systems, sub-system modules and piezo motor/drive components, optronics, medical, metrology, industrial applications, zoom lenses for film and digital cinematography applications.

Manufacturing

- **Manufacturing Machinery**, e.g. mould construction, tool making, forming machine tools, welding technology (for automotive industry and metalworking industries).
- **Automation of Industrial processes**, e.g. process control and yield management solutions, high-end computing, power conversion, industrial automation, IoT, motion and mechatronics, vision and sensing, and IT Integration.
- **Parts Manufacture**, e.g. design and manufacture of automobile parts and accessories.
- **Inspection Systems**, e.g. optical inspection systems, non-destructive X-ray technology inspection, and metrology technologies for advanced process control used in semiconductor manufacturing.

Health

- **Analytical Instruments**, e.g. design and manufacture of analytical instruments for biotech and biomed applications used within the academic & government, pharma/biotech, clinical diagnostic, and industrial markets, for instance for the identification and recovery of individual rare cells for molecular analysis and cell culture.
- **Hospital Diagnostics Machinery**, e.g. particle accelerators, energy and fusion technology, photon instrumentation, XUV and EUV solutions and systems, special manufacturing services and products, installation and commissioning.
- **Medical Devices for Monitoring**, e.g. design and manufacture of medical devices for monitoring patients within hospitals and remotely, precise scientific measuring instrumentation in the field of electrophysiology for research groups and for the pharmaceutical industry.
- **Medical Software**, e.g. cognitive analytics and solutions, IoT and Cloud technologies, computing as a service, healthcare informatics and cyber security.

Construction

- **Construction Equipment**, e.g. for mining and rock excavation, general construction and water infrastructure.
- **Building Automation**, e.g. energy management, lighting control, and access management.

Telecoms

- **Components and Systems**, e.g. providers of microwave and radio frequency components, antennas for automotive applications, high-efficiency power electronics and energy conversion.
- **Communications Technologies**, e.g. products that connect, protect and control critical applications in the commercial aviation, defense, space, medical, rail, wireless telecommunications and industrial markets, and enabling infrastructure for 5G, IoT, virtual reality and digital health.
- **Telephony Services**, e.g. mobile services, DSL data services and satellite services

Rail

- **Rolling Stock**, e.g. design and manufacture of rolling stock for rail and urban transport.
- **Signaling and Passenger Infrastructure**, e.g. design and manufacture of signaling and ticketing equipment.

Aerospace

- **Aircraft Manufacturing**, e.g. producers of aircraft.
- **Subsystem Development and Manufacture**, e.g. engine controls, aircraft components, electronic controls, flight deck, avionics equipment, navigation, environmental control systems, entertainment systems, electrical systems, and dependable networking (e.g. Time Triggered networking).
- **Air Traffic Management**, e.g. radar, control and display equipment.

Automotive

- **Vehicle Manufacturing**, e.g. premium and commercial vehicles development, production and sale of semi-finished products, buses and coaches, and other finished products, and the assembly of cars.
- **Subcomponent/system Research, Development and Manufacture**, e.g. automotive components, powertrain systems, materials labs., clean air and suspension technologies, ADAS and autonomous driving, Infotainment, V2X and IoT.
- Also represented were **Smart mobility** and **Financial Services**

Maritime

- **Design and Manufacturing**, e.g. autonomous/remote-controlled surface and underwater vehicles, and inspection TV cameras for offshore subsea intervention.

Energy

- **Renewable Energy**, e.g. manufacture, installation and servicing of wind turbines and installation of solar panels.
- **Energy Management**, e.g. air conditioning, heating for buildings, controlling electric motors, compressors, refrigeration for cooling food, energy management, software development, district heating and cooling infrastructure for entire cities and urban communities.

Other

Other stakeholder areas also identified were IT services, cyber security, finance, and retail technology solutions to support Hospitality, Wholesale and Digital Commerce.

3.1.4 Standards and Platforms

- Nokia – The Nokia Innovation Platform builds teams that create new solutions for the Internet of Things (IoT) [19].
- AVL Deutschland GmbH - provide an Integrated and Open Development Platform (IODP).
- Fujitsu – have a Windows Azure powered Global Cloud Platform in a partnership with Microsoft.
- Philips Medical Systems BV – provide the HealthSuite digital platform.
- Prodrive BV - have the Prodrive Motion Platform (PMP) which provides a platform for centralized, distributed and hybrid control.
- QINETIQ Limited – have a platform for Maritime Testing.

- Siemens - Railigent is a mobility platform that maps the entire data journey from track sensor to smartphone.
- Silicon Biosystems – have the DEPAArray™ platform and Ampli1™ genomic amplification kits. These enable automated identification, recovery and analysis of viable pure cells.
- Smartrac Technology Dresden GmbH – have the Smart Cosmos platform that manages living product data and integrates with existing digital systems for CRM, ERP, etc., by providing data virtualization and executing open-standard workflows between them when necessary.
- ST Microelectronics - provides a full hardware and software ecosystem to support rapid evaluation, prototyping and productizing of complete systems using the STM32 microcontroller with actuator, connectivity, sensor, power drive and standard I/O peripherals.
- Wapice OY – provide the IoT-Ticket platform (www.IoT-Ticket.com).

3.2 Survey of SMEs Engaged in CPS

3.2.1 Sectors Represented by SMEs

Figure 18. Representation of Sectors by SMEs

Figure 18 shows the representation of sectors by the 121 SMEs surveyed. Considering SMEs the majority of companies are engaged in multiple domains. The most active sector was transport which accounted for 24% of activities, followed by manufacturing at 19%. The Energy domain represented 15% of activities and the Health sectors 12% of activities. In addition to the main categories considered by Platforms4CPS a number of other sectors were also found. In this case these accounted for the majority of applications at 30%. This indicates the much wider diversity of activities performed by SMEs and the flexibility of the sector to cover many more areas that is not open to larger companies that address core business. The topics identified included communications, agriculture, ICT, smart commerce, consumer electronics, virtual and augmented reality, water, IoT, smart cities, robotics, identification, vending, public safety, security, software, marketing, photonics, electronics, flexible electronics, content integration, finance, payment systems, materials, food, access systems, home automation, people location and research services.

3.2.2 Country Representation

Figure 19. Country Representation by SME Stakeholders

Considering the country representation of SMEs it was noted that German SMEs are most active in the CPS area at a European level, however, there is more of a balance with also strong participation from French, Spanish, Austrian, Dutch, Norwegian and Czech companies. There is also more participation in terms of countries at a European level as shown in Figure 19.

3.2.3 Technology Domains

Semiconductors

- **Chip-Making**, e.g. deposition equipment for next generation thin film applications, LED, MEMS, CMOS, PowerIC and OLEDs, ion implantation, automation of material flows and handling processes, robotic handling equipment for highly sensitive environments, non-contact handling technologies (ultrasound-air-bearing) and automation support software.
- **Chip and System Design**, e.g. design tools for complex analog, RF and mixed signal IC development, specialised chip development for Smart Cities, mobility, energy and health sectors, and provision of security solutions.
- **Packaging**, e.g. consulting in the field of 3D and 2D packaging and surface mounting, development of printing technology solutions for flexible electronics.

Sensors and Actuators

- **Design and Manufacturing**, e.g. Industrial multiphysics CAE for vibroacoustic, piezoelectric, sensors, actuators, MEMS, optics for aerospace, defence, automotive and mechatronics applications, Silicon Drift Detectors (SDD), Silicon Photomultipliers (SiPM) for health and energy applications, machine vision for robotics and automotive, Millimetre Wave Integrated Circuits (MMICs) for high frequency radar solutions, phased-array-systems and wireless communications and packaging solutions for semiconductor devices, specifically (MEM's) sensors.

Hardware

- **Design and Manufacturing**, e.g. switch mode power technology for transport, energy, health applications as well as display technology.

Software and Embedded Systems

- **Software Development**, e.g. software for embedded systems used in machinery, medical, space, defence, and nuclear industries, embedded system product development, systems

engineering, operating systems for critical environments such as aerospace, medical instruments and industrial automation.

Testing

- **Development of Test Systems**, e.g. testing systems for high tech environments, quality control and in-line inspection processes, stationary and transient thermal characterization, non-destructive analysis by IR thermography and ultra sound temperature calibration.
- **Software Testing**, e.g. software development, test automation, functional testing and software quality for transport, manufacturing and health applications.
- **Virtual Testing and Modelling**, e.g. virtual product testing, model-based testing, thermal simulation, modelling consultancy, software simulation products and engineering services.

Information Technology

- **Information Technology (IT) Engineering**, e.g. development, implementation and integration of ICT systems, Web and Mobile design for enterprises, Integrated Development Environments for the design of complex systems, Internet protocol software and Internet consulting.

Manufacturing

- **Automation of Industrial processes**, e.g. development of drive systems, electric motors, magnetic gearboxes and drives for machines and systems, development and manufacture of machines and plants for the automation of production processes, systems integration, manufacture of electronic and electrical systems, smart sensors (vision and real-time radar sensors for harsh industrial environments), engineering consultancy for coordination of complex and distributed systems.
- **Parts Manufacture**, e.g. design and manufacture of automobile parts and accessories
- **Machinery Monitoring**, e.g. advanced monitoring of machine tools and analytical solutions using Big Data.
- **Optimisation**, e.g. software and consulting (business process optimization, personal service plan creation, production and logistics optimization), digital assistance systems, tools for managing supply chains and expertise for setting up world-wide manufacturing.
- **Simulation Services**, e.g. simulation services and simulation software, e.g. plant simulation.

Health

- **Medical Devices for Monitoring**, e.g. design and manufacture of medical devices for monitoring patients within hospitals and remotely via telemedicine, integration of systems, research and development of advanced microelectronics for health monitoring, indoor people localisation technology, e.g. patient bed monitoring, personalized care services and smart senior care, and real-time smart vision systems, access/attendance check systems.
- **Medical Software**, e.g. development of medical software, smart solutions for eHealth, welfare and personnel safety.

Automotive

- **Development and Manufacture of Automotive Electronics**, e.g. radar technology, embedded systems and systems integration.
- **Applied Research and Consultancy on ICT**, e.g. web and mobile solutions, wireless solutions, navigation technologies, Smart Cities, automated parking systems, autonomous driving, virtualization technologies, software solutions for gesture control and body tracking.

Aerospace

- **Avionics for Light Aircraft**, e.g. research and production of avionics equipment to assist the pilot.
- **Electric UAVs**, e.g. design of long endurance electrical airborne platforms based on advanced fuel cell technology for commercial applications.

Rail

- **Safety-Critical Software**, e.g. development of safety-critical software and systems for railways.

IoT

- **Product Development for IoT**, e.g. ultrasound and remote sensing for smartphones and IoT devices, smart and precise localization and motion data, mobile information systems such as Information Services, Mobile apps and Browsers, wireless IoT devices for use in manufacturing, transport and health domains.

Energy

- **Development of Control and Monitoring Systems**, e.g. electronics and embedded software development, systems integration for Smart Grid, renewables and Intelligent Buildings, mobile applications for supervision, IT solutions, consulting and training.
- **Electric Vehicle Charging**, e.g. smart charging controllers for Electric Vehicle charging networks.
- **Robotics**, e.g. mobile service robotics for nuclear applications.
- **Communications**, e.g. Powerline communication solutions.
- **Simulation**, e.g. software and services for testing compliance such as ElectroMagnetic Compatibility (EMC), electrical safety and thermal analysis.

Communications

- **Hardware Development**, e.g. design, development and manufacture of signal converters, RF modules, transimpedance amplifiers and related electronic products for communications, including test and measurement applications.
- **Software Development**, e.g. software engineering and integration for the telecommunication and broadcasting markets.

Other

Other areas identified as being of interest to stakeholders are security research and development, solutions for identification and localization, predictive analytics and event detection (which have application across many sectors). Supporting the ecosystem companies were also identified that provided help with marketing and finance, data science consulting and with commercialization of emerging technologies.

3.2.4 Standards and Platforms

- CAMEA, spol. sro - CAMEA Unicam is a platform for creation of multifunctional and scalable intelligent transportation systems (ITS) covering traffic safety, operations, maintenance and information.
- Greenflux Assets B.V. – produces a Cloud-based service and operations platform for managing large infrastructures of electric vehicle charging points over open protocols and systems, allowing every charge station to connect to the platform.
- Kinexon Industries GmbH – provides a sensor driven platform for real time location and motion analytics.

- Prediktor AS – provides the Apis real-time data management software-platform, used to log sensor and equipment values.
- RGB Medical Devices – are engaged in the EU CEN (European Committee for Standardization) TC251 for Medical Devices and interoperability, particularly in the elaboration of the ISO 11073 standard.
- RD Velho OY – produces 3 platform products: RD Cloud™, RD DA Platform™ and RD DOC™.
- Statwolf Ltd. – produces the Statwolf platform which is a smart, online platform for visualisation of data.
- SYSGO AG – produces the safety-critical, real-time operating system PikeOS and the Embedded Linux platform ELinOS.
- Systema Systementwicklung GmbH – produces a platform for end-to-end automation, manufacturing IT and enterprise integration solutions.
- Tellu AS – provides the TelluCloud Cloud platform for creating services and products with connectivity and Internet of Things functionality.
- THHINK Ltd. – provides a Cloud-connected smart wireless sensor platform that supports on-board and remote access to sensor data for transportation, energy, health and agriculture applications.
- Ulma Embedded Solutions COOP - works with standards such as, EN 50155, IEC 62304, EN 50128, ISO 26262, IEC 60730, EN 60601, UL 61010, ISO 13849, IEC 61508, etc.

3.3 CPS Priorities Identified by Large Industry, SME and Academic Stakeholder Groups

A stakeholder information gathering exercise was performed by Steinbeis2i at the Digital Innovation Forum event held in Amsterdam which brought together the ECSEL and ITEA communities. At this event participants were encouraged to vote for different topics that were of key interest to their organisations.

Figure 20. CPS Priorities Identified by Different Stakeholder Groups

The top ranked areas are shown in Figure 20. This indicated that there were marked differences in priorities for different stakeholder types, Large Industry, SMEs and Academic Organisations.

LI, SME & Acad	Cyber/Security, Privacy, Confidentiality, Trust Integration, Interoperability, Standards AI, Cognitive Systems, Autonomous Systems
LI	CPS Engineering (Requirements, Design, Testing)
LI & Acad	Safety, Reliability, Resilience, Fault Tolerance Modelling and Simulation (Virtualisation)
LI & SME	(Big) Data, Real Time Analysis, Visualisation
SME & Acad	Platforms, Reference Architectures, Tools Humans in the Loop Situational Awareness, Diagnostics, Prognostics, Decision Making and Support
SME	Human Machine Interface (HMI)

Figure 21. Ranking of CPS Priorities against Stakeholder Groups

The top scoring areas selected by Large Industry (LI), SMEs and Academia were ranked for each stakeholder group and then synergies between groups and subgroups were explored, for instance whether a particular CPS area was highly ranked by more than one group, or whether it was primarily the interest of a single stakeholder group. This led to Figure 21. This figure highlights that there are some key differences in terms of the priorities for different stakeholder groups. As one would expect large Industry alone is interested in CPS activities for systems integration. This is logical as this sector is the only sector capable of providing complete systems into this market. When it comes to data and HMIs SMEs see this as a priority and perhaps this indicates the market opportunity seen by smaller companies here. Academia and Large Industry see work on safety, fault tolerance, modelling and simulation as being important and here Large Industry traditionally relies on academic input looking for new approaches and methodologies. Both Large Industry and SMEs were very interested in exploitation of data, visualization approaches and real-time analysis and this is a key opportunity for providing products and services in the future. The SME and Academic community were both interested in the area of platforms and reference architectures. They were also interested in humans in the loop, situational awareness, diagnostics, prognostics, decision making and support. This reflects the opportunities for SMEs in this area and also the need for academic input to develop methodologies that support these areas.

All three stakeholder groups indicated the need for security, privacy and trust and also supporting standards for interoperability and integration. These currently represent fundamental roadblocks that need addressing. The area of AI, cognition and autonomous systems were seen as important by all three stakeholder groups indicating that this area is currently a very hot topic seen as a big opportunity for industry while at the same time requiring considerable research effort.

4 Existing industrial alliances

In this section key industrial alliances are considered that are relevant to the domains of CPS and also IoT.

4.1 Industrial Internet Consortium

The US Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC) [20] although originally American is now attracting members from all over the world. It is a non-profit organisation with 14 staff (See Figure 22).

Launched by AT&T, CISCO, GE, IBM and Intel, it is strongly tied to the Object Management Group (OMG). There are currently 130 members (20 from the EU) and it is growing quickly. There are 20 working groups. The consortium has developed use cases in healthcare, transportation, manufacturing and smart grid and 3 approved testbeds have been developed.

Figure 22. Industrial Internet Consortium

The initiative is addressing revenue generation, new operational efficiencies to drive down costs and improvements in customer satisfaction. This will create new markets and new working styles. Workforce productivity gains will be gained from digitalisation of tasks and reduced maintenance costs will result from use of predictive maintenance. Material and energy saving is also a key aim from reduced waste by precision monitoring to predict and control machines. There are working groups on security, technology, legal issues (e.g. who does data belong to), marketing and testbeds. Existing technology is used to identify research topics which are then investigated with the industrial members. It is not a standards organisation but it does evaluate and influence standards, e.g., ISO/IEC OMG and World Wide Web Consortium (W3C).

4.2 Allseen Alliance

Figure 23. AllSeen Alliance Structure

The AllSeen Alliance [21] is a non-profit consortium which is dedicated to providing an open environment for the Internet of Things to allow the widespread adoption of billions of products, systems and services (See Figure 23). The aim is to create a vibrant ecosystem and thriving technical community of hardware manufacturers and software developers who can create interoperable products that can discover, connect, communicate and interact directly with other devices, systems and services regardless of brand. This has been developed as part of the collaborative AllJoyn open source project, which provides an industry-supported software and service framework for smart connected products. The AllSeen Alliance organization is open and inclusive.

4.3 Open Interconnect Foundation

Figure 24. Open Interconnect Consortium Membership by Country

The Open Interconnect Foundation [22] (See Figure 24) was founded by major companies working on IoT chips, software, platforms and products for the Internet of Things to work together towards a single standard for IoT. It includes Intel, Microsoft, Samsung, Qualcomm, GE Digital and Cisco Systems. The aim is to come up with a single specification, or at least an open source common set of protocols and projects, for wearables, home appliances, industrial equipment, etc. and will provide Open Connectively Foundation, OCF-certified products. This should allow billions of connected devices (devices, phones, computers and sensors) to communicate with one another regardless of manufacturer, operating system, chipset or physical transport. The aim is to accelerate industry innovation and help developers and companies create solutions that map to a single open specification providing interoperability for consumers, business, and industry.

The Open Interconnect Consortium (OIC) and the AllSeen Alliance are currently joining forces in the OCF which brings together members of the two major rival organizations. Both groups have been promoting their own ways for connected devices to discover each other and determine what they can do together. All OIC members, including Intel and Samsung, are now part of OCF and two key members of AllSeen, Qualcomm and Microsoft, are now in the OCF. Microsoft has already stated that all Windows devices will in future interoperate with the OCF standard. Cisco and GE Digital have also joined OCF along with CableLabs, home appliance maker Electrolux and video and broadband company Arris Group. The OCF is promoting the IoTivity open source project [23].

4.4 Worldwide Alliances in IoT

Figure 25. Worldwide Alliances in IoT

In the IoT domain there are many world-wide alliances as shown in Figure 25. Many companies are promoting their ideas for the Internet of Things. One example is Intel who have developed an Intel IoT platform [24]. This is an end-to-end architecture based on secure horizontal and interoperable building blocks that functions as an IoT platform that can be deployed across industry sectors, e.g. manufacturing, utilities, healthcare, and public safety, and smart cities.

5 Roadblocks and opportunities for European technology companies

In this section opportunities for European technology companies are considered along with roadblocks that need to be addressed. The Market Segmentation report [1] identified a number of opportunities that exist for European SME's, Midcaps and Large Industrial Enterprises in the Automotive, Rail, Aerospace, Maritime, Manufacturing, Health and Energy sectors. These arise from increased automation, connectivity, optimisation of systems and processes (e.g. traffic management), health monitoring and also from services (e.g. mobility as a service) and infotainment. In the following sections each area is briefly described considering opportunities and roadblocks identified from the Market Segmentation in [1] and in analysis performed for this report.

5.1 Transportation

5.1.1 Road Traffic Management

Opportunity Traffic management is being driven by increasing demands for additional capacity, greater safety, and lower costs while meeting strict environmental regulations. The global car fleet is predicted to double from currently 800 million vehicles to over 1.6 billion vehicles by 2030 and without integration of information and flow control systems there will be severe congestion. Markets and Markets predicts that the global traffic management market is expected to grow from USD 4.12 Billion in 2015 to USD 17.64 Billion by 2020. A study by Frost and Sullivan [25] identified that for vehicle-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-infrastructure communications countries with significant private ownership of road infrastructure, e.g. France, Norway, Netherlands, Denmark, Italy, Sweden, are more likely to invest in cooperative systems infrastructure.

Roadblock Lack of a globally accepted communication standard for V2V and V2I that works in all the member states and also worldwide, covering Europe, America, Japan, and China.

5.1.2 Infotainment

Opportunity Driven by the Internet of Things the “Connected Car” is seen as a major business opportunity. BI Intelligence [26] predicts that 94 million connected cars will be shipped in 2021 and that connected cars will generate \$8.1 trillion between 2015 and 2020.

Roadblock Although the car companies are providing the connection interface in the car it is other companies that provide data services that are driving this change. There will be major competition from companies such as Microsoft, Apple, Pandora, Sprint, Google, etc.

5.1.3 Autonomous Cars

Opportunity Lux Research [27] predicts that the market for self-driving cars will be \$87 Billion by 2030. The revenues from this are expected to be \$24 Billion against a \$21 Billion US market and a \$20 Billion European market. The biggest opportunities for companies are in the software sector for autonomous driving software as this will be a differentiator and also key to safety. The software market is expected to grow from \$0.5 Billion today to \$10 Billion in 2020 and \$25 Billion in 2030.

Roadblocks The introduction of autonomous cars will happen in phases as the technology develops and users develop trust. The majority of the work is currently concentrated on technical solutions, e.g. processor architectures, sensor technologies, and data processing algorithms. The key challenge here is to make the technologies cheap and robust enough for mass usage. The certification of systems will be a challenge as the scope of the system is effectively unbounded and the number of eventualities is very large. It is expected that Google and IBM will be major players and competitors in the area of software. Another challenge is that car ownership is predicted to decrease in the future with more and more people using mobility solutions and services.

5.1.4 Rail

Opportunity There is great demand from the sector for 24/7 operation, high availability, low cost, safety, increased capacity for both passengers and freight, recovery from disturbance, and low carbon emissions. This is challenged by increasing congestion due to unprecedented numbers of passengers on existing infrastructure. There will be increased automation in regional, long-distance and freight rail services in the future. The urban transport market is predicted to grow at 3% overall between 2014 and 2020 and within this market, the share of fully-automated operation is expected to increase from around 30% today to around 70%. Markets and Markets predict that the railway management system market size is expected to grow from USD 29.27 Billion in 2016 to USD 57.88 Billion by 2021. Rail Traffic Management Systems (signalling, traffic control, routing, and train scheduling) will be the main opportunity as ERTMS is rolled out. The Internet of Things will be exploited for gathering maintenance data to improve the availability of vehicles and infrastructure through predictive maintenance, to create faster throughput in transport systems, to provide better resource management and to provide greater passenger comfort and convenience, through intelligent ticket and passenger information systems. The global high speed rail market presents the biggest opportunity in the rail market and the Urban Rail market is also growing. Within Europe Italy and Denmark will be key opportunities for rolling stock in coming years.

Roadblocks While the opportunities in Europe are strong, the Middle East and North America are the most attractive areas for global OEMs and there will be stiff world-wide competition.

5.1.5 Aerospace

Air Traffic Management Already air space is congested, and better coordination of aircraft will allow for increases in capacity and real-time deconfliction of flight paths. At a global level the Air Traffic Management (ATM) market is projected to grow from USD 50.01 Billion in 2016 to USD 97.30 Billion by 2022. This will be driven by an increasing demand for safe and reliable air traffic operations, increasing airspace congestion, development of new airport infrastructure, and modernisation of existing airports. The air traffic management market in India, China, and Japan is expected to witness significant growth by 2022.

Roadblocks There are competing approaches in Europe and the US for Air Traffic Management which lead to differences in equipment.

5.1.6 Commercial and Military Aircraft

Opportunity The commercial aircraft market is expected to grow driven by global gross domestic product (GDP) growth, relatively lower commodity prices including crude oil, and strong passenger travel demand, especially in the Middle East and Asia Pacific regions. The military aircraft market revenues are likely to grow at 3.2 percent in 2017 due to increased spending in the US, United Kingdom, France, Japan, and several Middle Eastern countries driven by heightened national security threats with governments equipping their armed forces with modern weapons, platforms and next-generation technologies, including cyber, intelligence gathering, defence electronics, and precision strike capabilities. Rising global tensions have also led to increasing demand for defence and military products in the Middle East, Eastern Europe, North Korea, and the East and South China Seas. This in turn has resulted in increased defence spending globally, especially in the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Saudi Arabia, South Korea, Japan, India, China and Russia. There are opportunities in flight control systems, more electric aircraft technologies, environmental control systems, aircraft electrical systems, electronic flight instrument system, aircraft health monitoring systems, airborne telemetry market and inflight entertainment market.

Roadblock Stiff competition from US companies and increasingly from China in the future.

5.1.7 Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

Opportunity According to Markets and Markets the global aerospace robotics market is expected to grow over the next decade to reach approximately \$7.9 billion by 2025. The UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) market was estimated to be USD 13.22 Billion in 2016 and is projected to reach USD 28.27 Billion by 2022. The drone software market was estimated to be USD 2.85 Billion in 2016 and is projected to reach USD 12.33 Billion by 2022, at a CAGR of 27.63% from 2016 to 2022. The drone services market was estimated to be USD 705.3 Million in 2016 and is projected to reach USD 18,022.7 Million by 2022, at a CAGR of 71.62% between 2016 and 2022. The military domain leads this sector, however, the commercial use of drones is also expanding for surveillance and monitoring in a number of domains such as search and rescue, policing and agriculture.

Roadblock Here there is currently a limit on the size of drones for safety reasons that can be operated without a pilot. Fundamental changes are needed from the certification authorities EASA and FAA to operate platforms.

5.1.8 Airport Management

Opportunity The ground handling and support software market is projected to grow from USD 2.49 Billion in 2016 to USD 3.25 Billion by 2022. The smart airports market is projected to grow from USD

11.31 Billion in 2016 to USD 14.87 Billion by 2021 driven by increasing passenger traffic, the need for check-in services upgrades, baggage handling services and improved security systems. The need to provide real-time information to passengers is further expected to drive the smart airports market.

Roadblock Investment in infrastructure at a national level in airports.

5.1.9 Maritime

Opportunity The growth in seaborne trade has averaged 4% per annum since the 1970s. The European maritime industry is spearheading environmentally friendly technologies and world-wide ship management systems are being linked with ship fouling efficiency metrics and navigation systems to optimize performance to reduce shipping costs, fuel consumption, and emissions. ICT technologies and algorithms are being used to optimize shipping movements and port operations. Safety-improved navigation systems and traffic management algorithms are being used for busy sea ways and ports. Looking to the future, it is expected that remotely piloted vessels will be adopted in a 10 year timescale in coastal waters, leading to remote piloting of vessels in the oceans by 2030, with a long term goal of fully autonomous vessels by 2035. The military ship building market has been affected by defence cuts but the overall market size is predicted to be \$838.2 Billion over the next decade.

Roadblocks Resistance to automation from safety authorities and also from seaman unions. Jones act [28] in the US.

5.1.10 Container Ships

Opportunity There are complex interactions in the movements of containers around the world to ensure that shipping and handling costs are minimized, with tight linkage into rail or road haulage networks. Efficient operations, fleet management, and the logistics of moving containers and goods is a key driver in the industry. Although management systems exist there is currently a fairly low level of use of ICT and little connection between systems. There are large potential opportunities in E-Maritime and Integrated Bridge Systems where the market was estimated to reach USD 5.60 Billion by 2021. The industry believes that the introduction of new ICT technologies for maritime traffic management will be key for safer and more secure operations allowing optimisation of shipping operations, voyages, condition-based maintenance and emissions reduction. Key enablers in the industry are the introduction of VSAT systems that provide connectivity to ships and much greater data rates for data transfer.

Roadblock Lack of standards and a clear view of what data should be transferred and how this should be used.

5.1.11 Unmanned Surface and Underwater Vehicles

Opportunity The unmanned surface vehicle (USV) market is projected to grow from USD 437.57 Million in 2016 to USD 861.37 Million by 2021 driven by increased demand for Intelligence Surveillance and Reconnaissance (ISR), water quality monitoring, maritime security and threats, ocean data collection and mapping. The Unmanned underwater vehicle (UUV) market is projected to grow from USD 2.29 Billion in 2015 to USD 4.00 Billion by 2020 driven by the needs of the deep water offshore oil and gas production industry, by the needs for protecting against maritime security and threats, and the need for ocean data and mapping.

Roadblocks In the defence sector work is largely funded at a national level. Ocean data collection is a growth area and notably companies such as Google are investing in this domain.

5.2 Manufacturing

Opportunity The industrial control and factory automation market, comprising control system manufacturers, field components manufacturers, system integrators, and software manufacturers, is projected to reach \$153.30 billion by 2022. By 2025 additive manufacturing is expected to create a €6.3 billion opportunity in the consumer electronics, automotive and aerospace industries. There is intense competition in this sector but a key driver is the 4th Industrial Revolution or Industrie 4.0. European companies have particular strengths in automation to improve the performance of production.

Roadblocks There is an increasing reliance and shift towards exploiting the Internet, e.g. Industrial Internet of Things. US companies dominate the Internet services domain and also business model innovations in this field. Security is now a key concern for interconnected systems.

5.3 Energy

The global investment in renewable energy is at a record level. For six years in a row the renewables sector has outpaced the fossil fuels sector for investment in power capacity additions. Wind and solar PV account for about 77% of new installations, with hydropower representing most of the remainder. Notably the world now adds more renewable power capacity annually than capacity from fossil fuels. The renewable capacity in place in 2015 was enough to supply an estimated 23.7% of global electricity, with hydropower accounting for 16.6% of this.

5.3.1 Wind Power

Opportunity The use of wind power has been steadily increasing over the past 10 years with capacity increasing by more than 700%. More than half of the world's wind power capacity was added in the last five years and wind supplied more new power generation worldwide than any other technology in 2015 with commercial installations in more than 80 countries. At the end of 2015, the leading countries for total wind power capacity per inhabitant were Denmark, Sweden, Germany, Ireland and Spain. Wind power is the leading source of new power generating capacity in Europe and the United States. In 2014, the market was dominated by the Asia-Pacific region, which had more than 54% of the total installed blades in the world. The region is projected to remain the most attractive market through to 2019. South America, the Middle East and Africa are also predicted to have promising growth rates. At the same time the microgrid market driven by rural electrification projects were valued at 16.58 Billion USD in 2015 and is expected by Markets and Markets to reach USD 38.99 Billion by 2022. The global small direct drive generator wind power market is estimated to reach USD 1.89 Billion by 2019, with a projected CAGR of 19.5%.

Roadblock China is a major competitor in the market and accounted for nearly half of global additions. GE is also a major manufacturer. However, there are also strong European manufacturers and many new markets are opening across Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Middle East.

5.3.2 Solar Photo Voltaic (PV)

Opportunity The annual PV market in 2015 was nearly 10 times the world's cumulative solar PV capacity of a decade earlier and increased by 25% in 2014 by 50 GW. China, Japan and the United States account for the majority of capacity added, but there are emerging markets on all continents. Uptake is being driven by the increasing cost-competitiveness of solar PV. Notably in China there is now 100% electrification of the country which has been achieved with significant use of off-grid solar PV. The global photovoltaic market is expected to grow at a CAGR of 18.30% between 2014 and 2020 and the overall market was estimated to be worth \$89.52 billion in 2013 rising to \$345.59 billion by 2020. There is a growing usage of photovoltaics in power plants, military applications, space & defence and industrial projects.

Roadblock The key players in the market are Chinese and Japanese. A challenge for the industry is that the prices of panels have reduced significantly as more panels have been mass produced particularly by Chinese companies. Despite this distributed rooftop solar PV is still more expensive than large-scale projects but the costs are reducing which would open up new markets.

5.3.3 Energy Storage

Opportunities An important sector linked strongly with the renewables sector is the area of energy storage and there are a range of energy storage technologies that are available. These include:

- **Solid State Batteries** - a range of electrochemical storage solutions, including advanced chemistry batteries and capacitors
- **Flow Batteries** - batteries where the energy is stored directly in the electrolyte solution for longer cycle life, and quick response times
- **Flywheels** - mechanical devices that harness rotational energy to deliver instantaneous electricity
- **Compressed Air Energy Storage** - utilizing compressed air to create a potent energy reserve
- **Thermal** - capturing heat and cold to create energy on demand
- **Pumped Hydro-Power** - creating large-scale reservoirs of energy with water

The predicted growth for each of these technologies is shown below.

Figure 26. Global Advanced Energy Storage Systems Market Capacity by Technology (Mega Watts)
(Source: US Energy Monitor 2017)

Although growth is expected in all markets and hydropower applications account for around 95% of existing energy storage, this report concentrates on storage technologies that can store energy from two key growth markets in renewables: wind and solar power. Energy storage is essential in these domains as the energy generation is intermittent. Driven by the take-up of renewable energy generation IMS Research predicts that the market for storing power from solar panels will grow from \$200 million in 2012 to \$19 billion by 2017 with major expansions being in Germany, U.S., Japan, and Italy. Another analysis company Navigant highlighted that 520 MW of new energy storage capacity was deployed globally in 2014 and 2015 and exponential growth is expected with a 47% increase in

capacity being added worldwide by 2020 equating to 29.4 GW. The compound annual growth rate is expected to be 60 percent. Taking the USA alone according to the Energy Storage Association (ESA) the U.S. market grew 284 percent in terms of megawatt-hours in 2016.

Lithium-ion battery storage is expected to take the majority market share in the sector, due to lower cost which is being driven down further by increased production demand. Bloomberg predicts that battery technology prices will fall to \$120 per kWh by 2030 compared with more than \$300 now and \$1,000 in 2010. The market is driven by three sectors: Utilities, Commercial & Industrial, and Residential. The utilities market is expected to account for 76% of the energy storage market in 2017 and notably more than 80 percent of the 520 MW of global storage deployments through 2014 and 2015 were made in the utility sector. 9,000 MW of new utility-owned storage capacity is predicted to be deployed by 2020. It is anticipated that the global installed energy storage for grid and ancillary services will grow from 1.1 GW in 2016 to 21.6 GW in 2025. The second largest market is expected to be the C&I sector with microgrid installations representing 21% of the market in 2017 and 37% by 2020. Finally, residential energy storage is expected to grow from approximately 95 MW in 2016 to 3,773 MW in 2025 with the leading market being in Germany. Already over 60 million Americans in 13 mid-Atlantic states plus the District of Columbia are using energy storage systems. In the EU, the “Clean Energy for all Europeans” package is likely to drive energy storage regulations.

Roadblocks An issue is that conventional models for electricity pricing, based on hourly intervals and considering generation versus demand fail to reward the benefits of energy storage for the grid. These benefits include speed and accuracy in delivery of ancillary services, reliability and resiliency. There is thus a problem of convincing investors to support the high upfront costs when the regulations and revenue streams are in the process of change and evolution. There is also existing regulations which act as barriers that prevent third party or customer ownership and competition in the energy, ancillary service and capacity markets.

The newness of the technology is also an issue with a lack of familiarity of the technologies amongst utilities companies, regulators and financiers as well as the lack of skilled technicians to maintain and operate systems. There are examples of success though such as in the US with the PJM region’s competitive market for frequency regulation compensation scheme. The same approach has been adopted for the UK National Grid and the first auction for 200 MW frequency regulation storage capacity in 2016 attracted over 1.2 GW in bids.

5.3.4 Smart Grid

Opportunities In the area of the Smart Grid there are major commercial opportunities for equipment makers, communication device players, and integrated solutions providers around the world. Across Europe there are many Smart Grid Initiatives looking at smart metering, integration of renewal energy and storage technologies, electric vehicle charging and integrated chips to enable transmission of digital information on the grid. For instance, SmartGrids France has funded a number of pilot projects testing the integration of solar PV and energy storage with the national grid using networked smart meters to monitor usage. In the UK the Green Deal programme is driving energy efficiency across the country with the aim of providing every home with a smart meter to help consumers understand their energy consumption and make savings. Outside of Europe there are massive investments in technology, e.g. India is spending US\$21 billion over the period 2015-2025 with an aim of stopping rampant electricity theft which is estimated to cost \$16.2 billion a year, the US is investing \$3.4 billion into Smart Grid projects, Australia (government and industry) has invested \$490 million into the Smart Grid, Smart City Program, Mexico plans a 30.2 million smart meter deployment between 2015-2025 with \$10.9 billion smart grid infrastructure investment, and Japan is installing 27 million smart meters by 2020 in advance of the Tokyo Olympic Games in 2020. However,

by far the biggest investment and opportunity comes from China where there is an initiative to construct power grids in the north-west province of Xinjiang to allow interconnection with the country's eastern provinces, Pakistan and other Asian countries. An Ultra High Voltage grid will be constructed to transmit power to the eastern coastal developed areas. The State Grid Corporation of China has allocated US\$31 billion to the Xinjiang Electric Power Company to perform grid integration of renewable energy and installation of power transmission lines by 2020. China also plans to construct a Global energy network by 2050 to meet global power demand using smart energy technology. The aim is to create grid interconnectivity with neighbouring countries such as Russia, Mongolia, Kazakhstan, Pakistan, Myanmar, Laos, Nepal and Thailand. Since 1992 China has relied heavily on electricity it purchases from Russia. China's annual predicted investment in smart grid development and related infrastructure from 2016 to 2030 is estimated to reach \$128 billion.

Roadblocks In order to get investors to commit funding there is a need for a regulatory framework for Smart Grids. The smart grid market is led by regulation and this varies considerably per country, particularly across Europe which has a big impact on possibilities for smart grid investments. It is difficult to copy results from field trials in one country to another country due to different regulations. Within Europe the Electricity Directive and the Energy Services Directive provide a mix of obligations and incentives to Member States to establish regulation targeted to encourage network operators to earn revenue not from additional sales but from efficiency gains and lower peak investment needs. To encourage this the European Commission and EFTA issued the Smart Grid Mandate M/490 in March 2011. Standards in the sector are voluntary and are developed by industry and market actors following principles such as consensus, openness, transparency and non-discrimination. In the smart grid area there is a need for standards for interoperability and safety. These are set by three European Standards Organizations (ESOs), the European Committee for Standardisation, CEN, the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardisation, CENELEC, and the European Telecommunications Standards Institute, ETSI. Cyber-security is also a key concern. Every asset of the smart grid (i.e., home gateways, smart meters, substations, control room) presents a potential target for a cyber-attack. A key concern is that an attack on a critical node may jeopardise grid security and lead a cascade effect and whole system blackout. Standards to develop smart grid cyber-security are already available, however, enhancements are needed to reflect the evolution of the smart grid, its technologies, and threats. A key challenge is to maintain these standards over time at an appropriate pace which requires considerable effort.

5.3.5 Medical Technology – Hospital Care

Opportunity Health care and long-term care expenditure accounted for 8.7% of GDP and about 15% of total government expenditure in the EU in 2015. Spending is rising faster than GDP and it is estimated that it will reach 16% of GDP by 2020 in OECD countries. Life expectancy currently increases with “one weekend per week” in Europe. The ageing population and prevalence of chronic diseases will increase public health and care budgets significantly due to the need to provide long-term care driving the need for new solutions. The healthcare IT market is projected to reach \$280.25 billion by 2021 from \$134.25 billion in 2016. The global medical device connectivity market is projected to reach \$1.34 billion by 2021 and the telehealth market is projected to reach \$9.35 billion by 2021.

The European medical technology market makes up 31 % of the world market and is the second largest medical technology market after the US (40%). 80% of the companies in the market are SMEs. Within hospitals curative care and rehabilitative care services account for more than half of current healthcare expenditure in a majority of EU Member States. Typical devices that are connected to patients employ proprietary systems and rely on trained professionals to operate the device and interpret system output.

Roadblocks There is a need for interoperability between devices as more devices are connected to

patients and also to existing hospital systems. There is also a need for V&V approaches and security as in many cases the devices are linked with safety-critical monitoring or provide information to doctors that could result in incorrect diagnosis or incorrect drug dosage. A challenge is that there are different regulation authorities and in the two key markets, the US and Europe.

5.3.6 Long Term Health Care and Home Care

Opportunity With the increasingly ageing population long-term care expenditure is rapidly rising. Providing care at home reduces hospital costs dramatically for patients with chronic illnesses and the elderly. Patients also prefer to be in their own home and this has benefits in terms of a patient's well-being. Systems can be used to provide remote monitoring of patients so that interventions are only made when needed. Other implanted devices, e.g. pacemakers, can also be monitored and there is a growing technological market in advanced prosthesis.

Roadblocks Devices need to be user friendly, unobtrusive (if possible) and need to be accepted by patients. There is a need for interoperability between devices to allow connectivity of different monitoring equipment both within the house and also to provide data to doctors for remote monitoring. If linked with chronic illness or implanted devices such as pacemakers there is a need for both appropriate V&V approaches and security. Regulation and approaches to liability will need to be developed to support the home use of medical technology.

5.3.7 Personalised Medicine

Opportunity Personalised medicine offers the opportunity to tailor diagnosis and drug interventions to individual patients based on feedback in response to dosage, predicted responses or risk of disease based on databases and models. There is heavy investment in this field within the pharmaceutical industry. This can be applied across many care areas such as cancer, cardiovascular, hypertension, and metabolic diseases. In order to support this there is a need for medical CPS/IoT sensors to collect patient data.

Roadblock There is a need for collection of large databases of information and also big data analytics in order to extract trends identify patterns or changes from normal status. This requires the infrastructure to collect and store data and also needs to address concerns over patient privacy.

5.3.8 Fitness and Wellbeing

Opportunity The wearable technology market is growing rapidly being worth \$28.7 billion in 2016, according to Gartner. Wearable devices are designed to sense and track data points such as body temperature, workout time, distance covered and heart rate. Most of these are worn on the wrist, but there are also a number of clip-ons, chest bands, leg bands, smart garments and ear-worn devices on the market. Wearables can be used to encourage healthy living and can also be used for healthcare monitoring. The wrist-worn wearables segment is the fastest growing market, at a CAGR of 30%. Apple shipped nearly 12 million Apple Watches and Fitbit shipped \$2 billion worth of fitness bands and other products in 2015. There is also an increasing market in smart T-shirts, body cameras, high visibility jackets, socks, shoes, bras and chest straps. Sportswear companies are highly active in this segment and are working on connecting fitness- and wellness-tracking devices with health-related software ecosystems.

Road Blocks Currently devices can be sold over the counter as they only make recommendations on fitness. Although sales have been positive with the major competitors shipping units fast: Fitbit (4.8 million units), Xiaomi (3.7 million) and Apple (1.5 million), if devices are to be used for healthcare there is a need for regulation and oversight via trained medical personnel. Medical devices are

strictly regulated by the US Food and Drug Administration and the European Commission. These already include healthcare wearables such as hearing aids and sensors that monitor heart rate, blood pressure and glucose. Privacy is a major concern and many devices can also collect “lifestyle medical” data in cloud software applications. The embedding of devices into clothing that needs to be washed introduces problems of longevity which are yet to be addressed.

5.4 Fundamental Roadblocks in CPS

Platforms4CPS held a workshop in Sweden in May 2017 [29]. At this workshop, several sessions were organised to discuss key roadblocks and challenges in CPS considering the trends towards Autonomous Systems, AI and Self-Awareness. The discussions highlighted that there are needs to consider not just the technology, but also cross-cutting topics such as security, assurance, liability, legislation, ethics, and end-user trust. As a result of the workshop a number of key roadblocks/challenges were identified which are detailed below:

5.4.1 Complexity

A key roadblock identified was the management of complexity at both the design stage and also in the operation of systems. This includes needs to deal with very many heterogeneous components and also very complex interactions with humans. There is a need for new approaches to Systems Engineering that can deal with decomposition into components to manage complexity.

5.4.2 Cyber-Security

There is a need for cyber-security and quick response to threats which may require reconfiguration. This ability to reconfigure adaptively directly conflicts with current approaches to functional safety.

5.4.3 Safety

There is a need to guarantee safety and provide certification approaches for machine learning algorithms even when it is not possible to understand all potential failure modes. As complexity grows so do concerns about dependability. New approaches are needed for composability of CPS.

5.4.4 Human Machine Interactions

Humans are an integral part of the system and may interact with the system in a number of ways. There are fundamental questions on the degree of automation required and how CPS and humans collaborate.

5.4.5 Integration with Legacy Systems

It is clear that new CPS systems will need to rely on and integrate with existing legacy systems. A key problem is that no one knows or understands the old system and models are rare. There is also a culture of companies not wanting to share information on existing systems.

5.4.6 Definition of Ethical basis for AI considering key rules that need to be adopted

With respect to AI there is a need to address ethical issues and support this with clear regulation to ensure that AI systems are acting in the best interests of people. One of the key problems is

transparency of what is encoded in the AI. In many systems there is a need to be able to ensure the completeness of the training set to ensure inclusivity (e.g. handicapped people).

5.4.7 Trust and Public Acceptance

There is a need to encourage public acceptance and trust for autonomous systems. For autonomous cars this is needed at the national and European levels to address different national driving styles and traits. Likewise there is a need to address trust in other sectors such as rail, aerospace and maritime.

5.4.8 Liability

There is a need to establish an approach to liability at a European level to cover the autonomous operation of vehicles.

5.4.9 Intellectual Property

An interface is required that provides a common language between components allowing understanding and exposure of information, without revealing all the content. This is important for a variety of reason including the protection of IPR. Here it is important to be able to provide information on what a component offers but also on the limitations that a component may have. This will require integration of computer science and physical aspects into one common notion of an interface.

6 Market opportunities for European solutions in the US

6.1 US orientations and trends

Within the US there are a number of activities underway in the area of CPS and IoT that support the indigenous ecosystem. A complication is that in some quarters CPS within the US is considered to be a subset of the IoT sector so in many cases it is difficult to separate out CPS and IoT research. At a foundational level CPS research is driven by NSF. At a higher level NIST has a leading role in the guidance of activities in the area notably producing a framework for CPS, however, at the highest level NITRD has the responsibility for coordinating CPS and IoT activities across all agencies.

6.1.1 NSF Foundational Research into CPS

Considering foundational research the NSF Cyber-Physical Systems programme [30] has so far funded over 300 projects. The goal of the NSF CPS programme is to develop the core system science needed to engineer complex Cyber-Physical Systems. The programme aims to create a research community committed to advancing research and education in CPS and to transitioning CPS science and technology into engineering practice. The multidisciplinary programme (control, computer science and communications) addresses cross-cutting fundamental scientific and engineering principles that underpin the integration of cyber and physical elements across all application sectors. Additionally, the programme supports the development of methods, tools, hardware and software components, prototypes and testbeds.

NSF is thus working closely with multiple agencies of the federal government within the US, including the U.S. Department of Homeland Security (DHS) Science and Technology Directorate (S&T); the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT) Federal Highway Administration (FHWA), and through FHWA, the U.S. DOT Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) Joint Program Office (JPO); the National

Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Aeronautics Research Mission Directorate (ARMD); several National Institutes of Health (NIH) institutes and centres [including the National Institute of Biomedical Imaging and Bioengineering (NIBIB), Office of Behavioral and Social Sciences Research (OBSSR), National Cancer Institute (NCI), and National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences (NCATS)]; and the U.S. Department of Agriculture-National Institute of Food and Agriculture (USDA-NIFA). This highlights the wide breadth of areas where CPS has a role. There are three classes of research and education projects that are funded by NSF:

- **Breakthrough** projects giving a significant advance in fundamental CPS science, engineering and/or technology that has the potential to change the field. This category focuses on new approaches to bridge computing, communication, and control. Funding for Breakthrough projects may be requested for a total of up to \$500,000 for a period of up to 3 years.
- **Synergy** projects to demonstrate innovation at the intersection of multiple disciplines, to accomplish a clear goal that requires an integrated perspective spanning the disciplines. Funding for Synergy projects may be requested for a total of \$500,001 to \$1 million for a period of 3 to 4 years.
- **Frontier** projects that address clearly identified critical CPS challenges that cannot be achieved by a set of smaller projects. Funding may be requested for a total of \$1 million to \$7 million for a period of 4 to 5 years.

6.1.2 NIST CPS Initiative

The NIST Engineering Laboratory, through the Cyber-Physical Systems and Smart Grid Program Office, is leading NISTs activities on Cyber-Physical Systems. In 2014 NIST formed the Cyber-Physical Systems Public Working Group (CPS PWG). This brings together experts to help define and shape key aspects of CPS to accelerate its development and implementation within multiple sectors. The CPS PWG has prepared a draft CPS Framework as shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27. NIST Framework for CPS

The CPS Framework (Framework for Cyber-Physical Systems, Cyber Physical Systems Public Working Group) [31] was developed in partnership with industry, academic and government experts and provides a methodology for understanding, designing and building CPS including those with multiple

applications. As CPS are multidisciplinary CPS research and standards development is carried out in multiple NIST Laboratories. This includes advanced manufacturing, cyber-security, buildings and structures, disaster resilience, and smart grid. A key goal is to design and develop a CPS testbed to characterise CPS equipment, systems, performance, and standards. NIST has also investigated the strategic importance of CPS and produced a report “Strategic R&D Opportunities for 21st Century Cyber-Physical Systems. Connecting computer and information systems with the physical world. January 2013” [32] which highlights the importance of the technology across a number of sectors including autonomous cars, robotic surgery, intelligent buildings, smart electric grid, smart manufacturing, and implanted medical devices. Key needs identified were:

- Robust, effective design and construction of systems and infrastructure - key to designing dependable systems from the ground up and reducing cost and time to market;
- Improved performance and quality assurance - essential for spurring future investment, acceptance, and use of innovative systems that promise to provide revolutionary improvements to conventional practice;
- Effective and reliable system integration and interoperability - required for highly connected and networked components to work together effectively as a total system; and
- Dynamic, multi-disciplinary education and training - will make possible sustained growth and innovation and spawn a new generation of entrepreneurs, as well as the next generation of cyber-physical systems.

6.1.3 NITRD Government Agency Coordination

Coordinating all activities across agencies NITRD has set up the CPS SSG [33]. This is responsible for coordinating programmes, budgets, and policy recommendations for Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS) research and development (R&D). This includes identifying and integrating requirements, conducting joint programme planning, and developing joint strategies for the CPS R&D programmes conducted by agency members of the NITRD Subcommittee (Federal IoT/Cyber-Physical Systems). The Cyber-Physical Systems Vision Statement document produced by NITRD provides a summary of the drivers, e.g. building controls, energy, transportation, healthcare and crosscutting strategic challenges such as cyber-security, privacy and social-technical aspects of CPS. The report also lists the technologies being explored and the multi-agency plans for CPS. Critically the report identified that although a number of federal agencies have independent research efforts to address CPS science and engineering challenges, there are still many gaps in the federal R&D portfolio.

R&D Gaps	DARPA	DBS	DOD/services	DOE	DOE/ARPA-E	DOT	FDA	NIH	NASA	NIFA	NSA	NIST	NSF	OASD (R&E)	Others
Mission R&D: Crosscutting Research and Development															
Core CPS Science and Technology – control, real-time computing, communication concepts, modeling, hardware, and software platforms. Advanced engineered systems: manufacturing, energy, medical devices, transportation	X							X			X	X			
Science of Security for CPS			X						X	X	X				
CPS Virtual Organization (CPS-VO)	X			X					X		X			X	
Complex systems, cascading failure, engineered resilient systems, fault identification, diagnosis and recovery	X	X						X			X			X	
Mission R&D: Sector-Specific Challenges															
Aviation safety, certification, enabling bold, visionary aviation systems and technology for a safe, efficient Next Generation airspace								X							
Intelligent transportation infrastructure systems, enabling technology for high confidence next-generation transportation (NextGen, automotive autonomy, intelligent vehicles)	X	X		X				X			X	X			
New control architectures/algorithms and power electronics for distributed generation, storage, and managed consumption		X	X					X			X				
Smart food systems that support safety, logistic efficiencies, cold-chain integrity, and traceability									X						
Time-critical systems, mixed criticality architectures, verification, aviation autonomy	X	X						X							
Rapid design and manufacturing of advanced CPS technologies. Rapid verification and real-time health monitoring and reconfiguration/re-verification. Application to autonomous systems	X	X						X							
Real-time physiological sensing, modeling, control, and feedback; advanced medical devices and system interoperability, integration, and certification							X	X	X			X			
Mission R&D: Crosscutting Standards-Based Platform Technologies															
Cyber-Physical Systems Engineering Testbed	X										X				

R&D Gaps	DARPA	DBS	DOD/services	DOE	DOE/ARPA-E	DOT	FDA	NIH	NASA	NIFA	NSA	NIST	NSF	OASD (R&E)	Others
Measurement Science and Standards for Model-Based Diagnostics & Prognostics, Time Synchronization, Industrial Cybersecurity													X		
Measurement Science and Standards for Quality Measurement Systems for CPS, Wireless Networking for CPS, Advanced Battery Technology for CPS, Multi-Physics Modeling and Optimization, Adaptive and Predictive Control in CPS													X		
Standards-Based Integrated Architectures and Prototype Platform for CPS	X								X				X		
Education and Crosscutting Research Centers															
Future of skills development and instructor resources for CPS including online CPS training and educational infrastructure resources (e.g., CPS virtual laboratory)	X								X				X		
Research and Infrastructure for innovation in Medical CPS Pilot							X	X				X	X		
CPS Outreach Centers (CPS Government, Industry, Academia cooperative research model)													X	X	
Industrial Internet Consortium	X												X		
Transportation CPS Pilot (NSF Engineering Research Centers model)						X		X				X	X		

Figure 28. Technical Gaps Identified by NITRD

These gaps identified by NITRD with respect to activities being undertaken in each agency are areas which may well be opportunities for European actors and notably there is a synergy with respect to research activities and roadblocks identified in Europe. There are many technical barriers to rapid, predictable development and deployment of CPS as shown in Figure 28. It has been realised in the US that it is not possible to address the gaps agency by agency, sector by sector, or company by company so a multi-agency, multi-sector comprehensive focus on crosscutting R&D challenges in CPS has been advocated. The idea behind this is that developments for unmanned aerial vehicles or self-driving cars for instance could also be applied in other domains. Likewise technology developed for secure reprogrammable networked medical devices could be used in the smart grid. Thus collaboration between industry, university and government contributors in private-public partnerships is being promoted and a number of funding schemes have been proposed. This is very similar to the ideas being promoted with Europe for Public Private Partnerships such as ECSEL, Clean Sky, etc.

6.1.4 IoT Sector

In the purely IoT sector developments in the US are being largely driven by companies with major players Google, Cisco, etc., who dominate the marketplace. Various consortia and alliances have been formed to promote the uptake of IoT in the US as highlighted in Section 4. The vital importance of IoT has also been acknowledged by the Department of Commerce and it has been made a top priority as part of the Department's Digital Economy Agenda.

6.2 US Automotive Sector

Transportation is responsible for 70% of petrol consumption in the US and is the second costliest expense for most American households [34]. President Obama made major investments in advanced vehicle and fuel technologies, public transit, and high speed rail under the Recovery Act. One goal was to have one million electric cars on America's roads by 2015 which was incentivised by tax credits. New fuel economy standards were also introduced for cars and trucks to raise average fuel economy to 35.5 miles per gallon by 2016. This is predicted to save 1.8 billion barrels of oil over the lifetime of the vehicles subject to the standard. The aim is to lower transportation costs, reduce dependence on oil, revitalise the U.S. manufacturing sector and provide more transportation choices to the American people. Steps have been proposed to improve the efficiency of all modes of transportation, air, road, rail and marine and to develop alternative biofuels.

The drivers in the US for intelligent transportation are similar to those in Europe, however, another key driver is homeland security. There is a desire to provide surveillance of roadways and also a means for mass evacuation of people in urban areas as a result of natural disaster or threat. Each state has an Intelligent Transportation Systems chapter that holds a yearly conference to promote and showcase ITS technologies and ideas. Representatives from each Department of Transportation (state, cities, towns, and counties) within the state attend this conference. The Department of Transportation (DOT) has defined a set of goals for the US transportation system:

- Reduce or eliminate deaths and serious injuries among all users of the transportation system – drivers, passengers, cyclists, and pedestrians
- Increase the reliability and efficiency of the transportation system – for the movement of both people and goods
- Drive innovation in the development of safe, affordable mobility options for all Americans
- Increase the service life and optimise the maintenance of transportation structures in a state of good repair
- Reduce the environmental and energy impacts in the development, operation, and maintenance and use of the transportation system
- Increase the resilience of the transportation system to withstand severe weather and climate change impacts.

Figure 29. Intelligent Transportation Systems

These goals are being supported by a number of initiatives. The ITS Joint Program Office (ITS JPO) [35], within the Office of the Assistance Secretary for Research and Technology (OST-R) has responsibility for executing the “Subtitle C- Intelligent Transportation System Research of Public Law 109-59 Safe Accountable, Flexible, Efficient Transportation Equity Act: A Legacy for Users, enacted August 10, 2005”. Specifically the ITS-JPO will:

“Conduct an ongoing intelligent transportation system program to research, develop, and operationally test intelligent transportation systems and to provide technical assistance in the nationwide application of those systems as a component of the surface transportation systems of the United States”

The office works with the Federal Highway Administration, Federal Motor Carrier Safety Administration, Federal Railroad Administration, Federal Transit Administration, Maritime Administration, and the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration to plan, programme, and execute the ITS Research Program (See Figure 29). The focus of the programme is on vehicle-to-vehicle and vehicle-to-infrastructure connectivity through the application of advanced wireless technologies. The ITS Research Program specifically develops and tests the underlying technology and applications.

Also supporting this is the State Smart Transportation Initiative [36] which is promoting transportation practices that “advance environmental sustainability and equitable economic development, while maintaining high standards of governmental efficiency and transparency”. The SSTI, housed at the University of Wisconsin, operates in three ways:

- As a community of practice, where participating agencies can learn together and share experiences as they implement innovative smart transportation policies.
- As a source of direct technical assistance to the agencies on transformative and replicable smart transportation reform efforts.
- As a resource to the wider transportation community, including local, state, and federal agencies, in their efforts to reorient practice to changing social and financial demands.

Also supporting the sector is Smart Growth America [37]. This is a national organization dedicated to researching, advocating for and leading coalitions to bring smart growth practices to communities nationwide. The aim is to use smart growth strategies to create transportation systems for businesses and communities. This includes coverage of transit options like buses, trolleys, subways, light rail, street cars and ferries. It is driven by the need to accommodate more travellers in the same space and create better options for travel between home, jobs and stores. There is also an aim to make neighbourhoods safer and more appealing. Notably there is a drive to avoid new construction, cut expenses and improve the environment. Communities can provide travel choices by making it easy for residents and visitors to drive, walk, bike, or take public transport.

Jointly the SSTI and Smart Growth America (SGA) have produced a handbook [38] that provides 34 specific recommendations to help state transportation officials position their agencies for success.

Figure 30. Smart City Challenge

Work on transportation is also being strongly supported under Smart City initiatives, there are many of these being undertaken across the US, however, in order to promote best practice the US Department of Transportation (DOT) launched a Smart City Challenge [39] (See Figure 30). This is targeted at mid-sized American cities (200,000 and 850,000 residents). The winning city receives \$50 million of funding to implement proposed ideas and create a model for other cities to follow. The funding comes from a public-private partnership between the DOT (\$40m) and Vulcan (\$10m) which is an investment vehicle founded by Microsoft co-founder Paul Allen [40]. The aim is to promote Intelligent Transportation Systems, connected vehicles and automated vehicles.

Figure 31. Technology Applications for Transportation

The U.S. Department of Transportation has also performed forward looking analysis which resulted in the Beyond Traffic report [41]. This outlines the expected trends in the transportation system over the next three decades (See Figure 31). The aim is to promote a national conversation about the future of the U.S. transportation system and objectively frame critical policy choices that need to be made. Beyond Traffic is structured into three parts. The first part discusses the major trends in the transportation system. The second part discusses the implications of these trends for each mode of transportation: highways, transit, pedestrian and bicycle, aviation, intercity and freight rail, maritime

and pipeline. The final part presents a future scenario and highlights policy options based on the implications of the trends.

In Europe work on autonomous cars is being driven by automotive manufacturers. Likewise in the US work is being driven by traditional manufacturers such as GM and Ford, but also strongly by new entrants, e.g. Tesla, and notably by software companies, e.g. Google, and mobility providers such as Uber. It was noted in the Market Segmentation Report [1] that software companies and mobility providers are likely to be the key winners in the autonomous car market.

Figure 32. Tesla, Uber, Google and OTTO Vehicles

Examples of some of these US autonomous vehicle activities are pictured in Figure 32 from Tesla, Google, OTTO and Uber. Notably there have been high profile accidents in the case of Tesla, Google and Uber highlighting some of the pitfalls of autonomous cars. Despite this companies such as Google have been very active lobbying American states, e.g. Nevada, Florida and California, to allow operation of autonomous cars. Here there is intense competition between Europe and the US and a number of roadblocks with respect to regulation and liability.

6.3 US Rail Sector

The US lags behind Europe and China in terms of its rail network [42]. The introduction of high-speed rail was one of President Obama’s signature transport projects and \$11 billion has been spent since 2009 on development of faster passenger trains. However, implementation was slowed down by Republican and community opposition. The money provided went into upgrading the existing Amtrak service, however, this only allows trains to go 110 miles per hour and does not provide high speed rail services (See Figure 33). Also none of the money went into services in the Northeast Corridor which is the most likely place for a high-speed rail line. Congress was subsequently asked for a further \$10 billion to support high-speed initiatives.

Figure 33. Amtrak's Acela near Baltimore. The 150 mph Acela Averages Only 80 mph on the New York to Washington Corridor. (Credit Luke Sharrett: The New York Times)

Notably there was opposition from Republican Governors in Florida, Ohio and Wisconsin, who all cancelled high-speed rail projects and returned federal funds after deeming the projects too expensive and unnecessary. The most likely and controversial high speed rail project to be implemented is the 520-mile route between Los Angeles and San Francisco which has begun track construction and put out bids to build the trains. The project will be partly supported by the states cap-and-trade programme which requires business to pay for excess pollution.

In Florida, a 125 mph train will be introduced by a private company, All Aboard Florida, but this will operate at much slower speeds between Miami and West Palm Beach, with a stop in Fort Lauderdale. An extension to Orlando is also planned. Although private, the builders have applied for a \$1.5 billion loan from the Federal Railroad Administration which must be paid back with interest over 25 years. Several counties along the route, however, are opposing the project.

In Texas, the private Texas Central Railway company, has proposed a high-speed rail line by 2021 with trains that could reach speeds of up to 205 mph using Japanese bullet trains. This would cut the trip between Houston and Dallas to 90 minutes.

All of these projects offer opportunities for European signalling and infrastructure companies, passenger ticketing and management, as well as locomotive and carriage manufacturers. Key players are GE, Siemens AG that has a manufacturing plant in Sacramento, Spanish high-speed train manufacturer Talgo that has a plant in Wisconsin, and Alstom SA that has a factory in Hornell N.Y.

6.4 US Maritime Sector

In 2009 IHS Global Insight completed a study for the Maritime Administration of the US Department of Transportation, titled "An Evaluation of Maritime Policy in Meeting the commercial and Security Needs of the United States" [43]. This highlighted that US maritime policy supported the nation's domestic maritime trades but did not support international shipping trade and policy reforms were needed. The Maritime Administration reacted by creating offices at major US gateway ports (See Figure 34), starting with 10 of the largest ports on the West, East and Gulf Coasts, the Great Lakes and the inland river system. These offices interact with stakeholders, including headquarters staff, state and local authorities, port operators, shippers and carriers to identify Federal and state funding and cooperate on planning, environmental and community projects.

Figure 34. Gateway Office Locations in the US

The aim is to identify bottlenecks and ways of improving freight movement. For instance, the Gateway Office in Southern California has worked with public and private sector participants to tackle congestion and better understand the connection between improved cargo flow, economic vitality, community improvement and environmental sustainability. The gateway in Anchorage is leading a public-private partnership with the Port of Anchorage to redevelop its port complex to enhance the transportation of goods within the state. This includes construction of new berths and piers, introduction of new container cranes, on-site rail and railroad trailers, and development of a modern container yard to improve efficiency and reduce truck traffic. This approach to port revitalization is expected to be replicated at other U.S. ports. Public Private Partnerships are seen as the key way of funding and developing ports within America [44].

Here there are major infrastructure funding initiatives such as the Transportation Infrastructure Finance and Innovation Act (TIFIA) programme that provides direct loans, loan guarantees and standby lines of credit as a result of the Fixing America's Surface Transportation Act (FAST Act) with \$1.435 billion in capital over five years. This can be used for surface transportation infrastructure including highways, passenger and freight rail, port access, public transit, intermodal freight facilities and international bridges and tunnels. To date, the TIFIA programme has provided \$22.7 billion in credit assistance to support more than \$82.5 billion in transportation infrastructure investments to help build 56 major transportation projects around the country [45].

At the maritime industry level the American Maritime Partnership (AMP) represents the domestic industry. It has 450-plus members including vessel owners and operators, shipboard and shoreside workers, shipbuilders and repair yards, equipment manufacturers and vendors, dredging and marine construction contractors, numerous maritime associations and national security organizations. A strong domestic maritime industry is seen as being critical for America's economic, national, and homeland security. This is supported by maintaining the Jones Act [28] as the foundation of America's domestic maritime policy. This requires that any vessel transporting goods or passengers between two points in the United States or engaging in activities in US waters must be US owned, US built, and US crewed.

The U.S. shipbuilding and repair industry supports jobs in all 50 states with a total of more than 110,000 jobs nationwide and contributes \$37.3 billion dollars to the national GDP. Currently there are 124 shipyards in the U.S., spread across 26 states, which are classified as active shipbuilders. In addition, there are more than 200 shipyards engaged in ship repairs or capable of building ships but

not actively engaged in shipbuilding. The federal government, including the U.S. Navy, U.S. Army, and U.S. Coast Guard, is an important source of demand for U.S. shipbuilders. While just one percent of the vessels delivered in 2014 (11 of 1,067) were delivered to U.S. government agencies, 10 of the 12 large deep-draft vessels delivered were delivered to the U.S. government: five to the U.S. Navy, four to the U.S. Coast Guard and one to the National Science Foundation. Over 80 percent of vessels delivered during the last five years have been inland tank and deck barges. Tugs and towboats showed the greatest increase in terms of vessels delivered in the period 2010 to 2014.

Imports of finished ships, inputs and repair services amounted to \$398 million in 2014, down from \$1.2 billion in 2013. Industry imports are limited by the Jones Act. Additionally, the defence sector remains the industry's biggest client, accounting for more than 70 percent of industry revenues. Defence contracts typically require access to sensitive military technology and information and as a consequence the U.S. government limits any foreign involvement in defence contracts.

6.5 US Aerospace Sector

Within the United States one organization, the FAA, oversees the operation of 350,000 airplanes and 18,000 landing facilities. The increasingly crowded skies is a worldwide concern and Air Traffic Management is a major topic on both sides of the Atlantic. The National Airspace System (NAS) in the US is the collection of all the components (airspace, facilities, equipment, services, workforce, procedures, etc.) that enable the US air transportation system. The equivalent of SESAR (the future European ATM) in the US is NEXTGEN [46]. NEXTGEN, is short for the "Next Generation Air Transportation System," and is a programme to comprehensively transform the NAS into a system to meet future needs that will be safer, more reliable, more efficient and which will reduce the impact of aviation on the environment. The system is due for implementation across the United States in stages between 2012 and 2025. A concern here from a global perspective is that the SESAR and NEXTGEN systems adopt fundamentally different approaches to air traffic management raising compatibility issues not only in terms of approaches but also in terms of equipment which makes selling into the US market difficult.

In the civil aircraft domain the main competitor to Airbus is Boeing. The Boeing Yellowstone project plans to replace the company's entire civil aircraft portfolio with advanced technology aircraft. New technologies to be introduced include composite aerostructures, more electrical systems (reduction of hydraulic systems), and more fuel-efficient turbofan engines (such as the Pratt & Whitney PW1000G Geared Turbofan, General Electric GEnx, the CFM International LEAP56 and the Rolls-Royce Trent 1000). Yellowstone is divided into three projects:

- **Boeing Y1**, to replace the Boeing 737, 757, and 767-200 product lines. The Y1 covers the 100- to 250-passenger market. Boeing submitted a patent application in November 2009 (released to the public in August 2010) for an elliptical composite fuselage. This is expected to replace the 737, however work on this has been delayed with the launch of the 737 MAX, an updated and re-engined version of the 737 Next Generation. Boeing now plans to develop a new aircraft to replace the 737 in 2030.
- **Boeing Y2**, to replace the 767-300 and -400 product lines and potentially the 777-200. It covers the 250- to 350-passenger market, and was the first completed Yellowstone project, with the launch of the Boeing 787 Dreamliner which competes with the Airbus A330, A340 and A350 families.
- **Boeing Y3**, to replace the 777-300 and 747 product lines. Y3 covers the 350–600+ passenger market competing with the Airbus A380 family as well as the A350-1000. The Boeing 777-8X and 777-9X were launched by Boeing on November 16, 2013 at the Dubai Airshow in the United Arab Emirates, with 259 orders.

In the military sector Boeing, Lockheed Martin, General Dynamics and Northrop Grumman are the main players and produce a range of aircraft that are sold internationally. Although the market has been depressed in recent years with the increase in defence spending in the US there is an opportunity for European companies. However, the U.S. government limits foreign involvement in defence contracts making access very difficult unless a European company already has a strong foothold in the US typically via acquisition of a local company, e.g. Rolls-Royce bought Allison Aero Engines.

Development of Autonomous Unmanned Vehicles is a very active on both sides of the Atlantic with many military programmes. As of January 2014, the U.S. military operates a large number of UAVs ranging in cost from a few thousand dollars to tens of millions of dollars, with aircraft ranging from less than one pound to over 40,000 pounds:

- 7,362 RQ-11 Ravens
- 990 AeroVironment Wasp IIIs
- 1,137 AeroVironment RQ-20 Pumas
- 306 RQ-16 T-Hawk small UAS systems
- 246 Predators and MQ-1C Grey Eagles
- 126 MQ-9 Reapers
- 491 RQ-7 Shadows
- 33 RQ-4 Global Hawk large systems

These are used in a variety of roles intelligence, surveillance, reconnaissance, electronic attack, strike missions, suppression or destruction of enemy air defence, network node or communications relay, and combat search and rescue. Here there are opportunities for European companies to provide sensors and flight control computer technology as well as other systems. Rolls-Royce for instance provide the engines for the Global Hawk via Allison.

A major growth area is expected to be in the civilian domain. While the larger companies are investigating these areas the markets for cheaper aircraft open up opportunities for smaller companies and new entrants in platforms and payloads. In the US, for instance, there is some activity from Amazon on developing drones for delivering parcels. A key barrier is the need for certification to operate larger UAVs in civilian airspace. This needs to be approved by the FAA in the US and by EASA in Europe. In addition national legislation is also likely to be an issue.

6.6 US Smart Energy

A key challenge in the US is that the grid infrastructure is largely outdated some parts being over 100 years old. The Energy Independence and Security Act of 2007 (EISA) [47] made it the policy of the United States to modernize the nation's electricity transmission and distribution system to create a smart electric grid. This coupled with the "The American Recovery and Reinvestment Act of 2009 (ARRA)" [48] accelerated the development of Smart Grid technologies with \$4.5 billion investment in total for electricity delivery and energy reliability activities. This includes programmes to modernize the electric grid and implement demonstration programmes. This was supported by President Obama who has put forward a vision of a clean energy economy in a State of the Union Address and the Administration's commitment in the "Blueprint for a Secure Energy Future" [49]. This outlines a three-part strategy:

- Develop and Secure America's Energy Supplies: To deploy American assets, innovation, and technology to safely and responsibly develop more energy and be a leader in the global energy economy.
- Provide Consumers with Choices to Reduce Costs and Save Energy: Volatile gasoline prices reinforce the need for innovation that will make it easier and more affordable for consumers

to buy more advanced and fuel-efficient vehicles, use alternative means of transportation, weatherise their homes and workplaces, and in doing so, save money and protect the environment. These measures help families’ pocketbooks, reduce our dependence on finite energy sources and help create jobs here in the United States.

- Innovate our Way to a Clean Energy Future: Leading the world in clean energy is critical to strengthening the American economy and winning the future. Achieve this by creating markets for innovative clean technologies that are ready to deploy, and by funding cutting edge research to produce the next generation of technologies. And as new, better, and more efficient technologies hit the market, the Federal government needs to put words into action and lead by example.

Considering Smart Grids projects, in particular, there are a number of government initiatives and policies including investment grants, totalling \$3.4 billion [50] as shown in Figure 35. This includes funding to promote energy-saving choices for consumers, increasing efficiency, and fostering the growth of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar. The grants follow an industry matching model, meaning that every private investment made is matched by federal grants. Development is driven by private companies.

Figure 35. US Energy Programmes

The White House also released a report in 2011 by the Cabinet level National Science and Technology Council (NSTC) highlighting “A Policy Framework for the 21st Century Grid: Enabling Our Secure Energy Future.” [51]. This outlines policy recommendations that build upon the Energy Independence and Security Act of 2007 and the Obama Administration’s smart grid investments. The report was prepared by the Subcommittee on Smart Grid of the National Science and Technology Council, Committee on Technology. It provides a policy framework that promotes cost-effective investment, fosters innovation to spur the development of new products and services, empowers consumers to make informed decisions with better energy information, and secures the grid against cyber-attacks.

The framework has four pillars:

1. Enabling cost-effective smart grid investments
2. Unlocking the potential for innovation in the electric sector
3. Empowering consumers and enabling them to make informed decisions, and
4. Securing the grid.

Each pillar supports a set of policy recommendations that focus on how to facilitate a smarter and more secure grid [52]. Standards for the Smart Grid have been identified as being critical in the EISA and 2011 NSTC report. Standards are needed to make sure that investment remains valuable in the

future and help with innovation, highlight best practice, support consumer choice and open global markets for smart grid technologies and create economies of scale to reduce cost.

Figure 36. DoE Smart Grid

The two largest initiatives within the US are the Smart Grid Investment Grant (SGIG) Program and the Smart Grid Demonstration Program (SGDP) (See Figure 36 and Figure 37). The DOE Office of Electricity Delivery and Energy Reliability (OE) is responsible for managing these five-year programs.

Figure 37. Smart Grid Initiatives

The DOE’s Office of Electricity Delivery and Energy Reliability holds regional stakeholder meetings, to stimulate peer-to-peer dialogue on smart grid deployments, share lessons learned, and help replicate successes. The DOE is expanding cooperative relationships with the National Association of Regulatory Utility Commissioners and the National Association of State Utility Consumer Advocates, to provide technical assistance and share information on consumer empowerment from Recovery Act projects. A Smart Grid Innovation Hub has also been set up. Other initiatives include grid research and design investments by the Advanced Research Projects Agency–Energy (ARPA-E), a Home Energy Education Challenge, consumer behaviour studies funded by the Recovery Act; and investment in smart grid technologies by the Department of Agriculture’s Rural Utilities Service (RUS) [53].

The Department of Energy Office of Electricity Delivery and Energy Reliability also launched a Smart Grid Integration Challenge for Cities in 2016 to recognise US cities as “smart city leaders” in implementing sensing, data sharing, and data analytics to achieve energy consumption reduction targets set by individual cities. Each winning city will serve as a model for replication in other cities. A key need in the smart grid domain are standards for interoperability and safety. A key difference between Europe and the US is that standards are voluntary in Europe and are developed by industry and market actors. To encourage the development of standards within Europe the European Commission and EFTA issued the Smart Grid Mandate M/490 which was accepted by CEN, CENELEC and ETSI. In the US EISA called for NIST and FERC to facilitate the development and adoption of interoperability standards. The NIST led smart grid interoperability process, aims to develop flexible, uniform, and technology neutral standards that can enable innovation, improve consumer choice, and yield economies of scale.

NIST has the primary responsibility to coordinate development of a framework that includes protocols and model standards for information management to achieve interoperability of Smart Grid devices and systems. NIST has developed a three-phase plan to accelerate the identification and consensus on Smart Grid standards, establish a robust Smart Grid Interoperability Panel (SGIP) that sustains the development of the many additional standards that will be needed, and to create a conformity testing and certification infrastructure. The progress made in Phases II and III of the plan are described in [54]. This report also presents a reference model, standards, gaps, and action plans. The processes established by the SGIP are now guiding standardization efforts across more than 20 standards-setting organizations. NIST's standards for the Smart Grid [55] are targeted at industry utilities, vendors, academia, regulators, integrators and developers, and other Smart Grid stakeholders.

In terms of accessing the US market the disparity in regulations and standards between Europe and the US makes it difficult for European companies to access the US market. For instance, the IEC standard is not compatible with UL94. A fundamental problem is that in the US there are bigger differences between voltage potentials. Although the functionality being provided for systems on both sides of the Atlantic are virtually the same the differences between standards in the EU and US mean that EU manufacturers need to develop totally new products for the US market. This places European companies at a disadvantage compared to US suppliers. In order to get UL certification it is necessary to pay US inspectors. In particular, there is a requirement for European factories producing a product to be re-certified annually which is very costly. A further barrier are the regulations for fire protection which are different in the US. This means that different non-flammable materials are required to make products for the US market.

There are, however, moves to coordinate activities at an international level. NIST and the International Trade Administration (ITA) have partnered with the Department of Energy to establish the International Smart Grid Action Network (ISGAN). This is a multi-national collaboration of 23 countries and the European Union. ISGAN is designed to complement the Global Smart Grid Federation which is a global stakeholder organization which serves as an "association of associations" to bring together leaders from Smart Grid stakeholder organizations around the world.

Security is another key concern and smarter grids lead to increased vulnerabilities from intrusions, error-caused disruptions, malicious attacks, destruction, and other threats. As the electric grid network is key to the operation of a country, cyber-security is a key topic on both sides of the Atlantic. The European Commission has put together a multi-stakeholder and multidisciplinary group of experts to discuss and work on relevant matters regarding the security and resilience of communication networks and information systems for Smart Grids across Europe. Although standards for smart grid cyber-security are already available these need to be maintained and enhanced as technology evolves. In Europe Alstom Grid, Intel, and McAfee produced a white paper on smart grid cyber-security. In the US the Administration has proposed specific cyber-security legislation to ensure that grid operators and all stakeholders have access to actionable threat information and provide support for research, development, and demonstration of cyber-security systems. The aim is to identify and prioritise relevant cyber risks - including malware, compromised devices, insider threats, and hijacked systems - and develop standards and guidelines that enable the design of effective plans for mitigating those risks. A number of threat warning bodies have been set up in the US, Electricity Sector - Information Sharing and Analysis Center, the United States Computer Emergency Readiness Team, and the National Electric Sector Cyber-Security Organization. The NIST Information Technology Laboratory (ITL), Computer Security Division leads the Smart Grid Interoperability Panel (SGIP) Cyber-security Committee (SGCC) which has produced the NISTIR 7628 Guidelines for Cyber-Security (Volumes 1, 2, and 3) which is widely used by utilities, vendors, and regulators in the US.

6.7 US Manufacturing Sector

Government influence on the US manufacturing sector is weak, with liberal labour laws and a free market economy. The only areas where significant spending is used to expand a leading position is in the areas of biotechnology and defence. Following the economic crisis, the priorities in the US have been on re-industrialisation of the country and job creation. The manufacturing sector in the US is supported via a number of initiatives and policies.

Manufacturing USA [56] is a network of regional institutes, each with a specialized technology focus with the aim to enhance industrial competitiveness, increase economic growth, and strengthen U.S. national security. The institutes share the goal to secure the future of manufacturing in the U.S. through innovation, collaboration and education. Nine manufacturing innovation institutes have been established, with six more planned by the end of 2017. Within each institute, manufacturers of all sizes partner with academia and government to share manufacturing technology and workforce challenges. The aim is to leverage existing resources at industry, academia, and government partners to collaborate on and co-invest in manufacturing innovation and commercialization. Each institute is designed to be a public-private membership organization that provides vision, leadership, and resources to its members. At a national level, Manufacturing USA connects people, ideas, and technology to solve industry-relevant advanced manufacturing challenges. Reaching across industries, Manufacturing USA brings members of the manufacturing community together to overcome technical hurdles and to enable innovative new products through the institutes. It seeks to restore US leadership in manufacturing by addressing shared manufacturing technology and workforce challenges. The goal is to establish an innovation community for the next generation of manufacturers, manufacturing supply chains, workforce development programs, and technological centres of excellence to the U.S. economy.

To help US industry compete at home and internationally the International Trade Administration (ITA) strengthens the competitiveness of U.S. industry, promotes trade and investment, and ensures fair trade through the enforcement of trade laws. ITA provides U.S. firms with the full suite of country-specific export promotion services and market access, execution of international trade and investment policies and promotion strategies and enforces US trade laws.

The US focus is on providing additional customer value, for example by means of innovative services. In particular there is a priority on the Internet of Things and business models with a direct impact on stimulating new business. A data driven service approach is being pursued within the free-market economy. Considering the US approach to Industrie 4.0 to create customer value and services, activities are characterised on the business side by implementation of intelligent technologies to add value for the customer. This plays to a strength of the US in Silicon Valley in the field of data-driven services. The focus is mainly on the realisation of new products and services, innovative business models and promises of benefits for the customer. Adding value for the customer through individuality, service or quality is understood as the primary function of Industrie 4.0 applications. The reduction of manufacturing costs is seen as secondary.

The US market offers opportunities for European companies especially in cases where Industrie 4.0 solutions require comprehensive domain knowledge in the field of production to enable performance increases. However, a challenge is that US companies and universities globally dominate business model innovations especially in the fields of Internet services and multimedia. An area where there may be opportunities for European companies is in IT security where existing Internet giants in the US have undermined political efforts in the area leaving systems at risk.

6.8 US Health Sector

The 2007 U.S. Economic Census showed that 14.33 million people in the US (about 12.7 percent of all employed civilians) are employed in the health care sector. There are 547,709 ambulatory healthcare service facilities, 6,529 hospitals, and 75,730 nursing and residential care facilities in the U.S. In 2007 the healthcare industry generated revenue of \$1.552 trillion with hospitals generating \$707.0 billion, ambulatory healthcare services generating \$672.4 billion, and nursing and residential care facilities generating \$167.9 billion. Notably the US spends a larger percentage of GDP and more per capita on healthcare than any other country. In 2009 \$2.5 trillion (17.3%) of GDP was spent on healthcare which is an average of \$8050 per person. As a result the US healthcare equipment and supplies market is the largest in the world with approximately \$121.3 billion in sales in 2009. This is growing and sale of medical devices sales are projected to reach \$185.9 billion by 2019.

A major issue currently at policy level is the situation with the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act, also known as Healthcare Reform (HCR). This was expected to increase the number of Americans covered by health insurance adding 32 million individuals by 2019 with a corresponding increase in the use of medical devices. With the advent of the Trump administration this has been subject to cuts with votes to repeal the Act. The House of Representatives is now focused on defunding major segments of the bill which has consequences for the industry as well as health provision in general.

In the US the need for standards for interoperability of devices is seen as key. To support this the Federal Health Architecture (FHA) (covering 20 federal agencies) is an E-Government Line of Business (LoB) initiative designed to bring together the decision makers in federal health IT for inter-agency collaboration. The idea behind this is to create more effective health information exchange, enhanced interoperability among federal health IT systems and efficient coordination of shared services. The FHA also supports federal agency adoption of nationally-recognized standards and policies for efficient, secure information exchange of health data. The Office of the National Coordinator for Health Information Technology's (ONC) is developing and harmonising domestic health IT standards. The body also has a wider remit to interface with health IT organizations at the international level to promote best practices and collaboration with other countries.

Considering the market it is notable that over the past decade the value of medical devices imported into the US has steadily increased. In 2008 imports were valued at \$33.6 billion (one-third of the entire market) and in certain market segments, e.g. surgical and medical instruments, there has been double-digit growth. There are, however, significant barriers for European companies entering the US market. The most critical one is US regulation and a Stanford University report highlighted that more than 75 percent of the cost of bringing a medical device from concept to the US market is spent clearing regulatory hurdles. Typically the average total cost to bring a low- to moderate-risk "510(k) device" from concept to approval was approximately \$31 million, with \$24 million of this required to support FDA dependent and/or related activities. For approval of higher-risk device "premarket approval (PMA) device", the average total cost from concept to approval was approximately \$94 million, with \$75 million spent on FDA activities. The time spent to obtain FDA clearance is also an issue. On average this takes 10 months from the first filing to clearance for a 510(k) application and 54 months from the first communication to clearance for a PMA submission. (In 2009, the FDA approved approximately 3,000 products under the 510(k) application process, but only 15 PMA submissions). This has led to companies seeking to use the 510(k) process for higher risk products. The FDA reviewed the approval process and in August 2010 proposed a new Class of medical device, Class IIb for implantable or life-sustaining/life-supporting products. The Innovation Pathway Program was also launched to speed up the review of new devices from 10 months to 5 months by engaging the FDA with device scientists in the early stages of development. In return the manufacturer gets a written agreement from the agency on a target approval date for the product. The FDA also set up a National Medical Device Registry with the aim to use Unique Device Identifiers for each medical product to assess post-market safety and effectiveness. The industry has a strong lobby in the US via Washington-based AdvaMed which is the largest medical technology association in the world.

AdvaMed provides the “voice” for medical device companies during policy debates and can influence the discussion and outcome of pending legislation and regulatory initiatives.

Another key issue in the US is Reimbursement. Approval of a medical device by the FDA does not guarantee that a third party payer (e.g., Medicare, insurance company, health plan) will provide coverage and reimbursement for that device. So a European Company has to also ensure that Reimbursement can be obtained for their products. Reimbursement rates for Medicare and Medicaid are made through the Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS). CMS makes coverage decisions that dictate what will be reimbursed by the government. This gives CMS the role of being a regulator and purchaser of medical devices.

6.9 Success stories of European technologies being exploited in the US

There are a number of notable success stories for European companies in the US. Large European corporations, such as Mercedes, Torres, Bosch, etc., have been able to grow and diversify their revenues by expanding their business into the US. However, it is more challenging for small or mid-cap companies to be successful in the US. There are a number of reasons for this which include money, time, culture, and understanding of the market and/or product. In this section a number of success stories for smaller companies selling into the US are presented which were identified by project partners.

6.9.1 TTEch

A good example of the success is the company TTEch [57]. This SME has strategically moved into different sectors with the support of a number EU projects and notably via the EMC2 and CRYSTAL projects funded under ARTEMIS. The company now has 300 employees and has been involved in over 100 EU projects. A number of successful products had been developed such as TTP for aerospace and TT Ethernet. The latter is now being used by Boeing, Airbus, and by NASA as the data bus for the Orion spacecraft which is the successor to the space shuttle. The company has also been successful in pursuing applications in rail, wind power and medical applications. The continued success of the company is being supported by engagement in projects concentrated on the next generation products developing time-triggered support for multi-core chips (TT-NOC) and TT Safety.

6.9.2 AVL

AVL [58] is the world's largest independent company for the development of powertrain systems for internal combustion engines as well as instrumentation and test systems. For more than 60 years AVL Powertrain Engineering has been a partner in the global automotive and mobility industry for the development of innovative powertrain systems. Activities cover a range of propulsion sources from diesel engines to electric drives, alternative fuels, control software, transmission systems and battery technologies.

Figure 38. Hybrid Powertrain

Via AVL Instrumentation and Test Systems and AVL Advanced Simulation Technologies the company can support the development of solutions for customers targeting CO₂ reduction, the increasing complexity of new powertrain systems and process efficiency to quickly launch new models. AVL has a comprehensive set of multi-dimensional simulation tools in a flexible and open environment enabling multi-disciplinary solutions. These allow virtual prototyping at the component and system level.

6.9.3 Trixell

Trixell [59] is a jointly-owned subsidiary of Thales (51%), Siemens (24.5%) and Philips (24.5%) with 410 employees, including 40% engineers and technicians. It is a world leader in the design and construction of digital detectors for medical radiology, under the Pixium brand. The company was founded in 1997 and is based in Moirans, France. Trixell S.A.S. develops, manufactures, and supplies X-ray flat panel digital detectors for the radiological imaging industry. It produces large-format digital detectors for radiography, fluoroscopy and cardiovascular applications. There are more than 50,000 Pixium detectors in service worldwide and the detectors are used in most of today's X-ray exams. Manufacturing is carried out in 4,000 square meter clean rooms, and the production lines are largely part automated. Thales has also partnered in a plant in the United States that manufactures amorphous silicon arrays which is a key component in digital detectors.

6.9.4 Prima Industries

The PRIMA Industries group [60] was set up in the 1980s and it has various areas of interest and products. The company makes and distributes industrial vehicle components, e.g. light fittings, to companies such as Iveco, Daimler-Chrysler, Scania, Deutsche Bahn, Komatsu, Volvo, Caterpillar, New Holland, Lamborghini Auto, Van Hool, etc. The company designs components and makes them in robot controlled injection moulding presses for plastic parts and three-axis automated machining centres for aluminium parts. A Testing Centre provides the necessary guarantee of sturdiness and functionality in compliance with quality regulations.

6.9.5 SYSGO

SYSGO [61] provides a certified RTOS Technology for Embedded "Hard Real Time" Systems. The company has more than 25 years of expertise in certifiable software. The PikeOS is a Hypervisor based separation microkernel designed for the highest levels of safety and security. It is fully customisable and can be deployed for ARINC 653, Linux, POSIX, AUTOSAR, RTEMS and PikeOS native with support for ARM, NXP, X86, Leon/Sparc processor architectures. The PikeOS Hypervisor has been certified on a wide range of projects using various certification standards including DO-178C, IEC 61508, EN 50128, IEC 62304 and ISO 26262. The RTOS is used by Airbus, Continental, Thales, Raytheon, Rockwell Collins, Rheinmetall, B. Braun, Miele, Rohde & Schwarz and Selex in Aerospace and Defence, Automotive, Railway, Industry and IoT applications.

6.9.6 NXP

A company that has been consistently successful in the US is the German company NXP which was a co-inventor of the Near Field Communication (NFC) Technology and a market leader for secure connectivity solutions for the Internet of Things. The company has been rated among the 20 most innovative companies in its area. This is particularly the case in the domains of secure communication connections for Industry 4.0 and autonomous driving. The company is also very active in developing secure communication solutions for the Internet of Things.

6.9.7 Barco NV

Founded in 1934 in Belgium, Barco currently has over 3000 staff and develops visual, sound and collaborative solutions. Via a partnership with Dell, Barco medical displays have had significant success within the US. These displays can be configured to be used in any department of a healthcare organisation. The technology from Dell and Barco is also being sold in Europe. Barco has been involved in over 20 ITEA projects and has been the recipient of an ITEA Achievement Award.

6.9.8 MEDTECH

Founded in 2002 in France, MEDTECH produces medical robotic technology that assists in brain and spine surgery. Their product ROSA Spine received FDA clearance in January 2016. Priced at about 600k EUR and widely used in Europe, it is now also being purchased in the US. This has been helped by similar technology from the company being made available at US universities.

6.10 Pitfalls and Success Factors for Entrants in the US Market

In order to understand any commercial market it is necessary to understand competitors in the market, price points, offering, speed of the market, performance, market share, key players, and distribution channels. Although there are similarities between European and US markets there are also significant differences which need to be taken into account. A key problem is that the US market is a much faster and quicker decision making market than Europe and there are also far more distribution channels available to sell by than in Europe. European sales personnel commonly spend some of their time on lead generation as part of their marketing function. This is not the case in the US, where the two activities are separated, and here channel partners and sales people expect leads to come from the marketing personnel. A consequence of this is that in the US more money and resources are needed in order to deliver to customers as more people are required. It is common for new entrants to the US market to underestimate the cost of start-up operations in the US and also the time to get a business up and running. Product lifecycles are also very short in many ICT areas. This requires more effort and resources on innovation in a market where there is aggressive competition.

6.10.1 Marketing Materials

Marketing is a key driver in the US and a lot of time and effort is expended in producing a comprehensive marketing pack. It is very important to have professional presentations, final product samples with final packaging, catalogues, videos and a marketing plan. The US market focuses more on how to sell a product than on the actual product specification itself. A key role of the Marketing and Sales departments in the US are to create advertising and promotional material and this is resourced with a high budget. A common failing is that European entrants try to use existing

European sales materials and website promotion. This invariably fails because the material is not adapted to the US market and the content needs to highlight more benefits such as the results of ROI studies. Little things like changing UK English to US English are also important.

6.10.2 Distribution Channels

To reach potential buyers there is a need to identify the right distribution channels for material. This can be done over the web, through independent representatives who have leads or directly by the manufacturer through its own representatives. In the US the Internet has an overriding role for product sale and distribution. Other distribution channels include demonstration at industry trade events, print media channels including newsprint, industry specific and business magazines and journals and television. Experience shows, however, that new products do not benefit from advertising in newspapers or on television.

6.10.3 Marketing Staff

In many cases initial ideas about setting up in the US arise from one potential customer. Experience shows that when setting up it is important to also have a plan for marketing beyond the initial customer in order to consider future and sustainable business. It is essential that a company employs someone with US marketing and sales experience. A problem here is that salaries for marketing staff are much higher than in Europe and so the budget for sales personnel needs to take this into account. An issue here is how to attract a first rate sales or marketing executive to work for a completely unknown European company. In many cases a consequence of this is that European companies hire second rate marketing staff which puts them immediately at a disadvantage. One approach that has been used successfully is to bring in high quality staff on a part-time or temporary basis to cover key needs such as marketing consultants, sales channel developers and technical writers to make the company appear to be local for American customers.

6.10.4 Product Pricing

The US market is more a “price point” and “volume” driven market, which may mean that a European product based on premium price or quality may not fit well. This means that a product marketing strategy that worked in Europe may need to be changed radically for the US market. In order to work out the price point it is important to perform market analysis of what US buyers will pay to get what is offered for sale considering quality, availability and delivery, along with expectations for any volume or other discounts.

6.10.5 Lead Time Comes First

The US market is very dynamic and innovative. Disruptive technologies have a limited period of time in which to establish a market before competing technologies arrive. US companies fully understand and exploit this lead time based on confidential know-how or patent protection. This is critical because it represents the difference between introducing a de-facto market leader and launching a product among a field of competitors already vying for market share. A key mistake that European companies make is to delay product introduction by over-engineering, designing for perfection or elegance allowing other competing products to get market share first.

6.10.6 Cultural Differences

In addition to cultural differences between Europe and the US there are also cultural differences at the state level. For instance customers in California are different from those in Texas so it is advisable to employ local consultants to perform market research and validation before talking with customers and potential partners.

6.10.7 Demographics

Large companies will sell across the US, however, smaller companies with new products entering the US market for the first time must consider demographics. To target resources effectively a small company must decide what geographic market within the US they can efficiently cover in terms of making themselves known and economically successful. There are important demographic differences between the EU and the US with respect to territorial size and population density. With approximately 9.1 million square miles, the geographic area of the US is approximately twice the size of the EU with approximately 4.3 million square miles. However, the population of the US is smaller than the EU with about 304 million compared with approximately 490 million in the EU.

In general there are thus more potential customers per square mile in the US, however, the nine states in the New England/mid-Atlantic region are among the ten states with the highest population density in the US. Combined these states contain approximately 170,000 square miles of the US land mass with average population density of around 560 persons per square mile. For a European company first entering the US market these demographics have a very significant effect on the choice of location and marketing strategy, as well as travel time required to meet customers.

6.10.8 Location of US Office

The location of a US Office for a European company is strategic as it affects choices in terms of travel, recruitment, availability of service providers, etc. For instance, unless engaged in the film industry or semiconductors it is not advisable for a European company to locate on the West Coast. The East Coast is far more attractive (a 6 hour time difference is easier to manage for meetings than a 9 hour time difference) and setting up near established high tech clusters, e.g. Boston for High-Tech in general, Washington, DC for government related businesses (incl. Telecom and Green Tech), Texas for energy, etc., offers better access to talent. Travel connectivity is also important and good airline connections via major multi-airline airports keep costs lower.

6.10.9 State and Federal Regulation

Finally, the requirements of local, state and federal regulations and laws must be taken into account. These laws and regulations not only define what a company may/may not do and sell but also to issues such as physical location and business hours of operation.

7 Conclusions

This report considers the European CPS ecosystem with an overview of support for the area in terms of EU programmes, Industrial Associations, PPPs and technology hubs. Technology providers who are stakeholders in the ecosystem have been identified and the technologies being provided or currently under development along with the target application domains have been extracted. Platforms that are being provided by these stakeholders have been identified. Various consortia and alliances that have direct relevance to the community are described including the US Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC), the AllSeen Alliance (dedicated to providing an open environment for the Internet of Things) and the Open Interconnect Foundation founded by major companies (Intel, Microsoft, Samsung, Qualcomm, GE Digital and Cisco Systems) working on IoT chips, software, platforms and products with the aim of working together towards a single standard for IoT.

Based on the outcomes of previous work on worldwide market segmentation, market figures and competition analysis, opportunities for European stakeholders are identified along with roadblocks that need addressing for the Platforms4CPS domains of transportation, manufacturing, health and energy. More fundamental roadblocks for CPS technologies have also been extracted from PlatformCPS workshops. Large Industry and SME stakeholders have been identified indicating the spread of activities across the Platforms4CPS domains as well as strengths in Europe. The areas of key interest for large industry, SMEs and Academia have also been identified from a survey performed by Platforms4CPS.

There is a major opportunity for European CPS companies in the US market and the report assesses the competition, roadblocks and opportunities for European technology in the US market. Notably there is a strong internal US ecosystem supporting the CPS domain in general with also DARPA and industry sectors providing strong support. There is considerable funding for foundational research from NSF and also coordination of activities across the CPS/IoT domain from NIST and NITRD. Although a number of federal agencies have independent research efforts it has been identified that there are still many gaps in the federal R&D portfolio which in turn can be considered to be opportunities for European companies.

Barriers and roadblocks have also been considered both in terms of the technologies and also with respect to entering the US market. Key challenges are interoperability of systems, standards and regulations. Here a harmonisation between the US and Europe is not only advantageous but strongly needed. Regulation also has a crucial role in the development of CPS and IoT such as implications for privacy and security where the increasing interconnectedness of systems leads to vulnerabilities to unintentional errors and cyber-attacks. There is also a need for business models and regulation to support market access.

The report concludes by identifying European success stories in the US highlighting a range of companies engaged across a diversity of sectors. Finally, common pitfalls are identified which are particularly relevant to SMEs leading to advice for new entrants to the US market.

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9 Appendix A: Survey of Large Industry and SMEs

9.1 Survey of Large Industry

	Company Name (Large Industry)	Country	Domain: Transport, Manufacturing, Energy, Health	Key Technology	Platforms	Standards	Comments	
1	X-FAB Dresden GmbH & Co. KG	DE	Transport, Manufacturing, Health	Analog/mixed-signal semiconductor applications.				
2	ACCIONA INFRAESTRUCTURAS S.A.	ES	Transport, Infrastructure	Construction, concessions, water, industrial and services.				
3	ADIXEN VACUUM PRODUCTS SAS	FR	Transport, Manufacturing	Manufactures vacuum pumps, leak detectors and plasma sensors. Developing products for the semiconductor industry, the automotive market and the public R&D.				
4	ADVANCED AUTOMOTIVE ANTENNAS S.L	ES	Transport	Antennas for automotive applications				
5	Advanced Mask Technology Center GmbH & Co. KG	DE	Manufacturing	Manufactures optical photomasks				
6	Airbus	FR	Transport, Manufacturing	Designs, manufactures, and sells civil and military aeronautical products worldwide. In addition to its primary civil aeroplane business, the company has two divisions for other products and services: Defence and Space and Helicopters.				

7	ALCATEL-LUCENT DEUTSCHLAND AG	DE	Transport, Energy, Health, (and Service providers)	Communications (From the enabling infrastructure for 5G, IoT, to emerging applications in virtual reality and digital health)	Nokia Innovation Platform builds teams that create new solutions for the Internet of Things (IoT) https://networks.nokia.com/innovation/platform			
8	AMS AG	AT	Transport, Manufacturing, Health (Industrial, Consumer, Automotive)	Semiconductor manufacturer				
9	ANSALDO STS S.p.A.	IT	Transport	Railway and urban transport				
10	APPLIED MATERIALS	BE, FR,IL	Manufacturing	Semiconductor, display, Roll-to-roll WEB coating, Energy, Automation software				
11	ASM EUROPE BV	NL, BE	Semiconductors	Supplier of semiconductor process equipment for wafer processing.				
12	ASML NETHERLANDS B.V.	NL	Manufacturing	Manufacturers of chip-making equipment				
13	Atlas Copco Airpower N.V.	BE	Manufacturing	Compressor Technique, Vacuum Technique, Industrial Technique, Construction Technique and Mining & Rock Excavation.				

14	AVL GMBH	DE, AT	Transport	Powertrain systems	Integrated and Open Development Platform (IODP)			
15	Baumann GmbH	DE	Manufacturing	Machinery, mould construction, tool making.				
16	BESI (AUSTRIA GMBH and Netherlands BV)	AT	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy	Supplier of semiconductor assembly equipment for the global semiconductor and electronics industries. Technologies are Die Attach, Packing and Plating.				
17	Brooks CCS GmbH	DE	Manufacturing	Semiconductor automation and life science solutions.				

18	BRUKER AXS GMBH	DE	Manufacturing, Health	Manufacturer of high-end analytical instruments used within the academic & government, pharma/biotech, clinical diagnostic, and industrial markets.			key application areas such as life science research, pharmaceutical analysis, applied analytical chemistry applications, materials research and nanotechnology, clinical research, molecular diagnostics and homeland defense.
19	CARL ZEISS SMS GMBH	DE	Manufacturing	Semiconductor manufacturing (Optics and photomask).			Strategic partner is the Dutch company ASML
20	CENTRO RICERCHE FIAT SCPA	IT	Transport	Vehicle research and innovation, Materials labs, Powertrain research and technology.			
21	Cytocentrics Bioscience GmbH	DE	Health	Biotechnology company			The company provides services, such as device services, planning, software development, equipment maintenance, cell line development, cell line optimization, instant cell production, screening services, simulation, assay development, functional design, feasibility study, product design and prototyping services.
22	DAIMLER AG	DE	Transport, manufacturing	Producers of premium and commercial vehicles, and financial Services.			
23	Dainippon Screen Deutschland GmbH	DE	Manufacturing	Semiconductor Production Equipment			
24	DANFOSS A/S	DK	Energy, Transport, Manufacturing	Cooling food, air conditioning, heating buildings, controlling electric motors, Compressors, Drives and powering mobile machinery. The company is also active in the field of solar and wind power as well as district heating and cooling infrastructure that targets entire cities and urban communities.			

25	ECA Robotics	FR	Transport, Manufacturing	Designs and manufactures autonomous and remote-controlled surface and underwater vehicles and inspection TV cameras for offshore subsea intervention.				
26	ELTEK AS	NO	Transport, Energy, Communication	High-efficiency power electronics and energy conversion within telecom and industrial applications.				
27	EV GROUP E. THALLNER GMBH	AT	Manufacturing	Lithography, bonding and imprint systems.				
28	FAGOR ARRASATE S COOP	ES	Manufacturing	Design, manufacture and supply of forming machine tools.				
29	FEI (Czech Republic s.r.o. and ELECTRON OPTICS BV)	CZ, NL	Manufacturing, Energy	Designs, manufactures, and supports the broadest range of high-performance microscopy workflows.			Ameriacn company (FEI Group). Scientific and Technical Instruments industry. Application knowledge in the materials	
30	FICOMIRRORS SA	ES	Transport, Manufacturing	Motor vehicle parts and accessories manufacturers industry.			Part of the Ficosa Group	
31	FICO-TRIAD SA	ES	Transport, Manufacturing	Designs and manufactures automobile parts.			Part of the Ficosa Group	
32	Freiberger Compound Materials GmbH	DE	Manufacturing	Compound semiconductor substrate supplier.			Applications wireless communications and optoelectronics.	
33	FRONIUS INTERNATIONAL GMBH	AT	Transport, Energy	Welding technology (automotive industry and metalworking industries) and photovoltaics, where it produces high-quality solar electronics and data monitoring solutions.				
34	FUJITSU SEMICONDUCTOR EUROPE GMBH	DE	Manufacturing, Transport	Designs and supplies semiconductor devices and systems solutions to the European automotive, communications, multimedia and industrial segments	Fujitsu has also launched a Windows Azure powered Global Cloud Platform in a partnership with Microsoft.			
35	GLOBALFOUNDRIES Dresden Module One LLC & Co. KG	DE	Transport, Communications	Technologies: CMOS, RF and ASICs. Applications in mobility, automotive, communications networks and data centers and IoT.				

36	Heraeus Quarzglas GmbH & Co KG	DE	Manufacturing, Transport, Energy, Health	Produce natural fused quartz and synthetic fused silica for the semiconductor and telecommunications industries as well as applications for the optical, chemical, and lamp industries.				
39	HSEB Dresden GmbH	DE	Manufacturing	Supplier in optical inspection, review and metrology.		Comply with the relevant SEMI standards, including S2/S8. CE conformity and UL/CSA compliance.	Design and manufacture tools, modules and OEM components for wafer sizes up to 450 mm and for any kind of large and flat substrates.	

40	HYPERTAC	FR	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy, Health	Provider of technically differentiated electronic components, subsystems, microwave and radio frequency products that connect, protect and control critical applications in the commercial aviation, defense, space, medical, rail, semiconductor test, wireless telecommunications, and industrial markets.			Smiths Interconnect's technology brands (EMC, HYPERTAC, IDI, LORCH, MILLITECH, RF LABS, SABRITEC, TECOM and TRAK)	
41	IBM ISRAEL - SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY LTD	IL	IT, Health	Cognitive Analytics and Solutions, IoT and Cloud Technologies, Computing as a Service, Healthcare Informatics, Cyber Security.				
42	IDEAS & MOTION SRL	IT	Transport	Automotive electronic applications			Design of silicon integrated circuits for the control of electro-actuators, and its further integration in automotive powertrain applications.	
43	INFINEON TECHNOLOGIES	DE, AT, IT, RO	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy	Semiconductor and system solutions				
44	IXION INDUSTRY & AEROSPACE SL	ES	Transport	Automation of industrial processes				
45	JENOPTIK Optical Systems GmbH	DE	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy, Health	Produces optics and optical systems				

46	JORDAN VALLEY SEMICONDUCTORS LTD	IL	Manufacturing	Provides metrology solutions for thin films based on novel, rapid, non-contacting and non-destructive X-ray technology for the Semiconductors industry.				
47	KLA-TENCOR CORPORATION	IL, DE	Manufacturing	Provider of process control and yield management solutions, partners with customers to develop state-of-the-art inspection and metrology technologies. These technologies serve the semiconductor, LED, and other related nanoelectronics industries.			KLA-Tencor Corporation is a global capital equipment company based in Milpitas, California	
48	LAM RESEARCH AG	AT, BE, FR	Manufacturing	Supplier of wafer fabrication equipment and services to the global semiconductor industry.			Headquarters: Fremont, California	
49	MAZeT GmbH	DE	Manufacturing, Transport, Health	Design and manufacture of advanced sensor solutions. Products include sensor solutions, sensor ICs, interfaces and related software for consumer, communications, industrial, medical, and automotive markets.			MAZet is now AMS Sensors Germany	
50	Medtronic	NL	Health	Medical device company.			Its headquarters are in Dublin, Ireland. Its operational headquarters are in Fridley, Minnesota. Medtronic is the world's largest standalone medical technology development company.	
51	MONDRAGON CORPORACION COOPERATIVA SCOOP	ES	Health, Energy	Four areas of activity: finance, industry, retail and knowledge.				
52	MONDRAGON SISTEMAS DE INFORMACION SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA	ES	Manufacturing (Automation)	IT Services				

53	MULTI CHANNEL SYSTEMS MCS GMBH	DE	Health	Development of precise scientific measuring instrumentation in the field of electrophysiology for research groups at universities and for the pharmaceutical industry (key technology: non-clinical microelectrode array electrophysiology).			<u>Since Oct. 2014 MCS is a division of Harvard Bioscience, Inc</u>	
54	Murata Electronics Oy	FI	Manufacturing	Designs and manufactures silicon-based capacitive sensors for the measurement of acceleration, pressure, inclination, shock, vibration and angular rate.				
55	Nanomotion Ltd.	IL	Manufacturing, Health	Designs and manufactures advanced motion systems, sub-system modules and piezo motor/drive components. Applications from optronics to semiconductor, from medical to metrology and other industrial applications.			A Johnson Electric Company	
56	NOVA MEASURING INSTRUMENTS LTD	IL	Manufacturing	Provider of metrology solutions for advanced process control used in semiconductor manufacturing.			Nova's headquarters are located in Rehovot, Israel	
57	NXP SEMICONDUCTORS NETHERLANDS BV	NL	Transport	Automotive (ADAS and autonomous driving, Infotainment, V2X), IoT.				
58	OKMETIC OYJ	FI	Manufacturing	Silicon wafers				
59	ON Design Czech s.r.o.	CZ	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy, Health	Semiconductor				
60	ON SEMICONDUCTOR BELGIUM BVBA	BE	Transport, Energy, Health	Semiconductor				
61	PAC TECH - PACKAGING TECHNOLOGIES GMBH	DE	Manufacturing	Provider of advanced wafer bumping, packaging and solder ball placement equipment			Member of Aeneas	
62	PHILIPS	NL	Health, Energy	Electronics, healthcare and lighting	HealthSuite digital platform			

63	PICOSUN OY	FI	Manufacturing, Health	Supplier of high quality Atomic Layer Deposition (ALD) thin film coating solutions for industrial production				
64	PLANSEE SE	AT	Transport, Manufacturing, Health	Plansee High Performance Materials is an expert in the field of molybdenum, tungsten, tantalum, niobium and chromium components.			Industries: mechanical engineering, automotive, consumer electronics, medical technology, power engineering, construction and aerospace.	
65	PRODRIVE BV	NL	Transport, Manufacturing, Health, Energy	High-end computing, power conversion, industrial automation, IoT, Motion and mechatronics, vision and sensing.	Prodrive Motion Platform (PMP) - One platform for centralized, distributed and hybrid control			
66	QINETIQ LIMITED	UK	Transport	Defence, Cyber Security	Maritime Test Facilities			
67	RI Research Instruments GmbH	DE	Manufacturing, Health	Develops, designs, manufactures and tests high performance components and systems in research, healthcare and industry. Key technologies: Particle accelerators, Energy and fusion technology, Photon instrumentation, XUV and EUV solutions and systems, Special manufacturing services and products, Installation and commissioning.				
68	ROBERT BOSCH GMBH	DE	Transport	Automotive components, industrial products, building products.				
69	Rolls-Royce	UK	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy	Engineering company focused on world-class power and propulsion systems. The RollsRoyce Group is organised into five customerfacing businesses: Civil Aerospace, Defence Aerospace, Power Systems, Marine and Nuclear.				

70	S.O.I.TEC SILICON ON INSULATOR TECHNOLOGIES SA	FR	Transport, Manufacturing, Health	Generating and manufacturing high performance semiconductor materials			Soitec's semiconductor materials are used to manufacture chips which equip smartphones, tablets, computers, IT servers, and data centres. Soitec's products are also found in electronic components used in cars, connected objects (Internet of Things), as well as industrial and medical equipment.	
71	SEMILAB FELVEZETO FIZIKAI LABORATORIUM RESZVENYTARSASAG	HU	Manufacturing, Energy	Design, produce and sell metrology equipment for the characterization of semiconductor and photovoltaic materials, for monitoring the manufacturing process of semiconductor devices, flat panel displays and solar cells, and also for R&D purposes in these areas.				
72	SICK AG	DE	Manufacturing, Transport, Energy, Health	Manufacturer of sensors and sensor solutions for industrial applications. The company is active in the areas of factory and logistics automation and process automation.				

73	SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT	DE	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy, Health	Electrification, Automation and Digitalization				
74	SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT	DE	Industry, Energy, Healthcare, and Infrastructure & Cities	Industrial manufacturing	Railigent is a mobility platform that maps the entire data journey from track sensor to smartphone.		MindSphere – Siemens Cloud for Industry to optimize your repair and maintenance	
75	SILEX MICROSYSTEMS AB	SE	Health, Manufacturing, Transport	MEMS process technologies. Markets and applications: Consumer, Life Science & Medical, Telecom, Industrial & Automotive.				

76	Silicon Biosystems	IT	Health	A biomedical company, develops and provides technology for the identification and recovery of individual rare cells for molecular analysis and cell culture.	DEPArray™ platform and <u>Ampli 1™</u> genomic amplification kits enable automated identification, recovery and analysis of viable pure cells. The flexibility of the DEPArray™ system is enabling researchers around the world obtain results in a wide range of applications.			
77	SILTRONIC AG	DE	Transport, Energy	Hyperpure silicon wafers			Hyperpure semiconductor silicon wafers form the basis of the most complex semiconductor components, including high-voltage applications, low resistivity devices in automotive engineering and telecommunications as well as large-scale integrated microprocessors and memory modules for information processing.	
78	SMARTRAC TECHNOLOGY Dresden GmbH	DE	Manufacturing, Transport, Health, also (Retail, Media, Electronics &Gaming, Animal Identification)	RFID products and IoT solutions	Platform (Smart Cosmos) manages living product data and integrates with customers existing digital systems for CRM, ERP, etc., by using powerful data virtualization and executing open-standard workflows between them when necessary.		Markets: Animal Identification, Automatic Vehicle ID Systems, Automotive Industry, Car Access, Electronics & Gaming, Healthcare, Industrial Applications, Media & Document Management, Retail, Sports & Entertainment, Supply Chain & Asset Management.	
79	SOFRADIR	FR	Transport+C83	Designs and manufactures infrared detectors and other detector for military, space and commercial applications.			The company's shareholders are Thales, Sagem and Areva	
80	Solteq Oyj	FI	Transport(Automotive retail)	Retail technology solutions (Hospitality, Wholesale, Digital Commerce).				

81	SONY DEUTSCHLAND GMBH	DE	Manufacturing	Electronics			Business: TV & Video, Audio, Digital Camera, Professional Products & Solutions, Medical, FeliCa (contactless IC card technology), Semiconductors, Smartphones & Internet, Game & Network Services, Pictures, Music, Financial Services.
82	SPTS Technologies Ltd	UK	Semiconductor and microelectronics	etch and deposition wafer process solutions			
83	STMICROELECTRONICS	FR, IT	Manufacturing, Transport, Energy, Health	Electronics and semiconductor manufacturer.	ST and its partners are providing a full hardware and software Ecosystem to support rapid evaluation, prototyping and productizing of complete systems using the STM32 microcontroller with actuator, connectivity, sensor, power drive and standard I/O peripherals.		STMicroelectronics is a French-Italian multinational electronics and semiconductor manufacturer headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland.
84	TeamNet World Professional Services SRL	RO	Manufacturing	IT Integrators			Aiming at integrating the GIS technology with the UAV systems in order to deliver full solutions or to design a Cloud platform accessible to the SMEs in Romania. Also, specialized in the design and implementation of the SCADA automatic control systems.
85	TELECOM ITALIA SPA	IT	Telecommunications	Telephony services, mobile services, and DSL data services			
86	TENNECO AUTOMOTIVE EUROPE BVBA	BE	Transport, Manufacturing	Clean air and suspension technologies			
87	THALES ALENIA SPACE ESPANA, SA	ES	Transport, Security	Air Traffic Management, Flight deck, avionics equipment & functions, Flight Avionics, InFlyt Experience, Electrical Systems, Training solutions, Navigation solutions, Support & Services.			

88	THALES ANGENIEUX	FR	Manufacturing	Designs and develops zoom lenses for film and digital cinematography applications.			Thales Angenieux SA operates as a subsidiary of Thales SA	
89	TOKYO ELECTRON EUROPE LIMITED	FR	Manufacturing	Semiconductor production equipment			Supplies a wide range of semiconductor production equipment (SPE) and provides service and support to global semiconductor device manufacturers	
90	TOPPAN PHOTOMASKS FRANCE SAS	FR	Manufacturing	Photomask technology				

91	TTTECH COMPUTERTechnik AG	AT	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy	Dependable networking solutions based on time-triggered technology and modular safety platforms.			Deterministic Ethernet, Time-Triggered Protocol (TTP), Guarantee of Service for Real-Time IoT, Advanced Driver Assistance Systems	
92	UNITED MONOLITHIC SEMICONDUCTORS SAS	FR	Transport	RF Products, Solutions and Foundry Services			For Telecom infrastructure, Space, Defence and Security, Automotive Radar and Industrial sensors	
93	VALEO EQUIPEMENTS ELECTRIQUES MOTEUR SAS	FR	Transport	Powertrain systems, smart mobility				
94	VDL Enabling Technologies Group B.V.	NL	Transport, Manufacturing	Development, production and sale of semifinished products, buses & coaches and other finished products and the assembly of cars.				
95	VESTAS WIND SYSTEMS A/S	DK	Energy	Manufacturer, seller, installer, and servicer of wind turbines.				
96	WAPICE OY	FI	Transport, Energy	Software development and electronics design services	Uses various coding platforms, also the company has IoT-Ticket platform (www.IoT-Ticket.com)			

9.2 Survey of SMEs

	Company Name (SMEs)	Country	Domain: Transport, Manufacturing, Energy, Health	Key Technology	Platforms	Standards	Comments
1	3DiS Technologies	FR	Semiconductors	3D interconnect technologies for Wafer-Level integration of 3D System-in-Package and high performance 3D inductive passive devices			
2	ABINSULA SRL	IT	Transport, IoT	Consultancy in automotive and embedded integration fileds, web & mobile applications and their customization.			
3	ABSINT ANGEWANDTE INFORMATIK GMBH	DE	Transport, Energy, Communication	Provides advanced development tools for embedded systems, and tools for validation, verification and certification of safety-critical software.			
4	ACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES SRL	IT	Transport	DACs technology design			The disruptive AT DACs technology is also combining great performance Value and cost effective solution for industrial application such automotive and Power combining best in class performance and price solution.
5	ADVANCED PACKAGING CENTER BV	NL	Semiconductors	Advanced packaging for MEMs, sensors, photonics, power and complex IC's			
6	Advanced Vacuum Distribution Europe AB	SE	Energy	Provider of plasma processing and vacuum testing systems, as well as software and hardware upgrades for vacuum equipment			Serves multiple markets, including failure analysis, R&D, solid-state lighting, renewable energy, nanotechnology, photonics, and environmental control systems
7	Afore Oy	FI	Manufacturing	Services, tools and equipment for testing sensor in development.			MEMS sensor Test Solutions.
8	Agileo Automation	FR	Manufacturing	Industrial automation with a high expertise in software services for semiconductor and photovoltaic equipment manufacturers			Develop software products to help semi-conductor equipment manufacturer.

9	AITIA INTERNATIONAL INFORMATIKAI ZARTKORUEN MUKODO RT	HU	Telecom Network	Research and development of network monitoring and analysis, and has special expertise in testing the core of mobile telecom network and developing value added network solutions.			
10	ALLIANCE POUR LES TECHNOLOGIES DE L'INFORMATIQUE	FR	Transport	Software publishing company in functional validation, safety analysis and system engineering of increasingly complex and interconnected systems			Model-Driven Engineering. ALL4TEC has been developing its expertise throughout various domains such as Transportation, Defence or Information Systems, and telecom.
11	AMBIESENSE LTD	UK	IoT	Mobile information systems: Information Services, Mobile apps and Browser, Wireless IoT devices, Big data and search, remote sensing and CPS, Smart-field monitoring			
12	AMIC Angewandte Micro-Messtechnik GmbH	DE	Transport, Health	Product engineering			Microsystem technology, Automotive, Information and communication technology, Material research and development, Aerospace, Microsensors und –actors, Nanotechnology.
13	AP&S International GmbH	DE	Semiconductors	Designs and produces batch- and single wafer wet process solutions for surface treatment of substrates under cleanroom conditions for customers worldwide			
14	APOJEE	FR	Transport, Industrial	Supplier of high-technology in the fields of power electronics, embedded control units and ignition / combustion.			
15	APSI3D	FR	Energy	aPSI3D (agile Power Switch 3D-Integration) is specialized in Electronic Low Inductance High Power Modules which enables compact, lighter and more efficient electrical power inverters.			
16	ASYS AUTOMATIC SYSTEMS GMBH & CO KG	DE	Manufacturing	Designs and manufactures vacuum and cleanroom robots and assembly modules.			
17	Automatix Sp. z o. o.	PL	Transport, Manufacturing, Health	Provides solutions in the manufacture and testing of software, drivers, complex control systems, and SCADA systems.			Aerospace, defense, electronic, telecommunications, railroads to medical device manufacturers.
18	Bag-era	FR	Manufacturing	Computer science engineering consulting firm, specialized in dependability and coordination of complex or distributed systems.			The LINC environment eases the development and deployment (into production) of distributed applications.

19	BCB Informatica y Control S.L.	ES	Manufacturing, Transport, Energy	System Integration			Specialized in system integration in the fields of communications, automatic test equipments (ATEs), machine vision, industrial automation, instrumentation and data acquisition systems. Focusing in electronic systems, BCB is specialized in IT (mainly, phone and multimedia systems) and in automotive industries (CAN/ LIN buses, clusters, multimedia, durability tests, etc.). And Solar systems.
20	BERLINER NANOTEST UND DESIGN GMBH	DE	Services	Stationary thermal characterization, Transient thermal characterization, Non-destructive analysis by IR thermography, Ultra sound Temperature calibration, Thermal simulation, Software development			Specialised in services for reliability of micro and nano compounds.
21	BetterSolutions S.A.	PL	Transport, Manufacturing, (and agriculture)	Development and implementation of high quality ICT systems.			Focuses on geographic information systems, telematics and complex solutions for logistics, agriculture, industry and smart cities.
22	BNEARIT AB	SE	Transport	Project Manager, Requirements analyst, System architects, Team leader, System Developer, Test Manager, Tester, Configuration management			
23	CAMEA, spol. s r.o.	CZ	Transport	Smart Cities	CAMEA Unicam is a state-of-the-art and field-proven platform for creation of multifunctional and scalable intelligent transportation systems (ITS) dedicated to the road traffic market sector including traffic safety, operations, maintenance and information.		
24	CISC SEMICONDUCTOR GMBH	AT	Semiconductors	Semiconductor company			
25	CLEARSY SAS	FR	Transport	Development of safety critical software and systems mainly in the railways			
26	Comlight AS	NO	Energy	Control Systems			Advanced technology of Comlight’s control system “Motion Sensing Street lighting” that really big savings can be achieved.
27	Conformiq Software Oy	FI	Manufacturing, Transport, Health	Software technology company, focused on test automation, functional testing and software quality			Banking, Insurance, Retail, Telecom operators & equipment, Manufacturing, Embedded.
28	CRYTUR SPOL.S.R.O.	CZ	Manufacturing	Synthetic crystal manufacturing and processing			
29	DEVOLO AG	DE	Energy	Powerline communication solutions			
30	DIGISKY SRL	IT	Transport, Manufacturing	Light aircraft manufacturers. Handle the whole industrial process, from initial research up to the full production of avionics equipment (EFIS) to assist the pilot in all phases of flight.			
31	Electromagnetic Compatibility MCC bv	NL	Energy	ElectroMagnetic Compatibility (EMC), electrical safety and thermal analysis			

32	Elliptic Laboratories AS	NO	Communications, IoT	Ultrasound sensing for smartphones and IoT devices			
33	ENGINE POWER COMPONENTS GROUP EUROPE S	ES	Transport, Energy	Manufacturer of Engine Camshafts and Balance Shafts			
34	EVIDENCE SRL	IT	Transport, Communications	Open source embedded systems			Automotive, Communication & Media, Control systems, Digital home.
35	EVOLARIS NEXT LEVEL GMBH	AT	Smart production, smart commerce	Digital assistance systems in the industrial and commerce sector			
36	EVOPRO INNOVATION KFT	HU	Transport, Energy, Manufacturing	Industrial Automation, Nuclear & Big Physics, Automotive Systems, Embedded Systems, Software Systems			
37	Fabmatics	DE	Semiconductors	Automation of material flows and handling processes in the semiconductor industry and other high-tech production environments			
38	Fent Innovative Software Solutions SL	ES	Transport, Manufacturing and consumer electronic	Offers technological solutions specifically designed for real-time embedded and critical systems using virtualisation technologies			Delivering products into the Aerospace, Aeronautics, Automotive & Transportation, Industrial Automation, Network Equipment, and Consumer Electronic markets.
39	GEORGII KOBOLD GmbH & Co. KG	DE	Manufacturing	Develops and produces drive systems, electric motors, magnetic gearboxes and drives for machines and systems			
40	gestigon	DE	Transport, consumer electronics, virtual & augment reality	Develops software solutions for gesture control and body tracking based on 3D depth data			Automotive, Virtual & Augment reality, consumer electronics, embedded systems.
41	GREENFLUX ASSETS B.V.	NL	Energy, Transport	EV-solutions for charging networks. Developed a cloud based smart charging platform and as smart charging controller.	Cloud-based Service & Operations platform. The platform manages large infrastructures of charge points over open protocols and systems, allowing every charge station to connect to the platform.		
42	greenpower technologies	ES	Energy	Renewable energy grid integration			
43	GUEP Software GmbH	AT	Energy, water	Software Engineering, IT Solution Design, Consulting & Training			
44	HELIOX BV	NL	Transport, Energy, Health, also display and video	Specialized in switch mode power technology			
45	IDEAS & MOTION SRL	IT	Transport	Automotive electronic applications			Design of silicon integrated circuits for the control of electro-actuators, and its further integration in automotive powertrain applications.
46	INGENIA-CAT S.L.	ES	Transport	Motion control			Applications: Motor integration, robotics, packaging.
47	INNOSENT GMBH	DE	Transport	Radar technology			Automotive and industrial sectors. Home automation, security, sport.

48	Inras GmbH	AT	Manufacturing	Development of real-time radar sensors suited for applications in harsh industrial environments.			
49	INSTITUT MIKROELEKTRONICKYCH APLIKACI S.R.O.	CZ	Identification, vending, security, health	Solutions for identification and localisation.			Family Home, Apartment Building, Company, Industrial Site or Factory, Public Building, School, Healthcare Facility, Parking Lot, Custom Development
50	INTEGRASYS SA	ES	Telecom systems, avionics, software engineering	Software development, engineering and integration company specialized in the telecommunication and broadcasting markets.			
51	INTEGRATED SYSTEMS DEVELOPMENT S.A.	EL	Manufacturing, health	Integrated Systems			Acts as an original electronic equipment developer and integrator. ISD is also actively involved in the field of telemedicine.
52	ION BEAM SERVICES	FR	Manufacturing	Manufacturer of new-generation equipment, such as PULSION [®] and IMC [™] validates its leadership in ion implantation technology			
53	IQUADRAT INFORMATICA SL	ES	E-commerce, marketing	Web design			

54	ISTITUTO SUPERIORE MARIO BOELLA SULLE TECN	IT	Smart Energy, Smart City, Smart Health	Applied research on ICT: Advanced Computing and Electromagnetics, Applied Photonics, Innovation Development, Mobile Solutions, MultiLayer Wireless Solutions, Navigation Technologies, Pervasive Technologies			
55	ITML	EL	Transport, Energy, Health	Software solutions to enterprises, in the Web and Mobile domain			Telecommunication networks and services, energy efficiency, transportation and healthcare.
56	KETEK	DE	Health, Energy, Photonic applications	Developer and manufacturer of Silicon Drift Detectors (SDD) and Silicon Photomultipliers (SiPM)			SDDs can be found in X-ray fluorescence spectrometers & electron microscopes – and our new Silicon Photomultipliers in all kind of photonic <i>applications</i> .
57	Kinexon Industries GmbH	DE	Manufacturing, Transport, Health, media	Smart & Precise Localization & Motion Data.	Sensor driven platform for real time location & motion analytics.		Industries such as production, logistics, healthcare, sports & media.
58	LABORATORIOS ALPHA SAN IGNACIO PHARMA S.	ES	Health	Design, development and production of medical diagnostic device.			
59	LAKESIDE LABS GMBH	AT	Communications, Robotics, Transport	Hub for science and innovation in self-organizing networked systems.			
60	LANGE RESEARCH AIRCRAFT GMBH	DE	Transport, Energy	Design long endurance electrical airborne platforms based on advanced fuel cell technology for commercial applications.			Applications: Border security, Search & Rescue, Environmental exploration, Protection.
61	LINUS AS	NO	Telecommunications	Telecommunications			

62	MAGILLEM DESIGN SERVICES SAS	FR	Electronics, Industrial Systems and Content Integration.	Information technology (IT). Designs and markets an Integrated Development Environment for the design of complex systems based on the notion of Internet protocol (IP) blocks.			The Magillem environment is dedicated to the design, verification and flow management of complex HW/SW based on IP-XACT
63	MICRAM MICROELECTRONIC GMBH	DE	Communications and test & measurement applications	Designs, develops, manufactures, and distributes signal converters, RF modules, transimpedance amplifiers, and related electronic products for communications, and test and measurement applications.			
64	micro analog systems oy	FI	Semiconductor company				
65	MICROELETRONICA MASER SL	ES	Transport, Energy, Health	Focuses in three globally operating business sectors in the frame of Smart Cities: Mobility, Energy, Living.			Products: Control & power electronics for Electric Vehicles, Control electronics for Automotive & Railway, PV Power Plants, CSP Plants, 3G autonomous dataloggers for Water Cycle monitoring, Mobile Telecare system with fall detector, Sensing and communication system for Smart Cities.
66	MIXED MODE GMBH	DE	Transport, Manufacturing, Health, Energy (also telecommunication and security)	Embedded & Software Engineering.			Industrial, Automotive/Transport, Telecommunication, Semiconductor, Medical Industry, Aerospace, Security, Energy.
67	MOVATION AS	NO	Innovation	Independent support arena for entrepreneurs.			InnoBørs - norwegian independent innovation stock exchange.
68	NANO DESIGN SRO	SK	Health, home automation, Access and attendace check	Research and development of advanced microelectronics.			Development of advanced technologies based on the latest electronic devices, circuits and systems, eg. noninvasively human body monitoring in real time, access and attendance of employees, home automation.
69	NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO	NL	Health, Energy, Industry, Defence, Safety and Security, Urbanisation	TNO is a knowledge organisation for companies, government bodies and public organisations. Focus areas: Industry, Healthy Living, Defence, Safety & Security, Urbanisation, Energy.			
70	NXTCONTROL GMBH	AT	Manufacturing	Industrial automation			IEC 61499, IEC 61131 and object – oriented engineering with integration from field to SCADA level for your industrial control offer (for manufacturers of control hardware components.
71	NXTECH AS	NO	Manufacturing, Transport	Developing ideas into products, managing supply chains and setting up world wide manufacturing.			SW and electronics development, mechanical and industrial design, automotive.

72	OPEN ENGINEERING	BE	Transport	Industrial Multiphysics CAE for vibroacoustic, piezoelectric, Sensors , Actuators, MEMS, FSI, Optics for aerospace, defence, automotive and mechatronics applications.			
73	PACKAGING SIP	FR	Semiconductor	Consulting on the field of 3D and 2D packaging, and surface mounting.			

74	pi4_robotics GmbH	DE	Manufacturing, Transport, Health, Energy	Machine Vision and robotics.			Plate glass, Automotive, Electroplating, Electronics, Ceramics, Plastics processing, Life Sciences Medical technology & pharma, Fuel cell, Photovoltaics.
75	PREDIKTOR AS	NO	Software solutions	IT Software	Apis real-time data management software-platform, used to log sensor and equipment values.		Industrial software solutions for optimizing production, Apis real-time data management software-platform, NIR spectrometer and related software solutions, Non-invasive glucose measurement device.
76	qplox engineering bvba	BE	Energy, Transport, Health (Pharma, medical and bio), Consumer electronics, Food, Materials	Development of test and automation systems for high tech environments.			Fields: Test systems development, PCB Prototyping, Control systems, Software development, Data management, Consulting
77	QRTECH AB	SE	Transport, Energy	Specialists in electronics and software.			
78	R G B MEDICAL DEVICES SA	ES	Health	Telemedicine technology.		Closely involved in the EU CEN (European Committee for Standardization) TC251 for Medical Devices and interoperability, particularly in the elaboration of the ISO 11073 standard	
79	RD VELHO OY	FI	Industrial Internet	Product development and IoT.	Platform Products: RD Cloud™, RD DA Platform™, RD DOC™		Developing embedded systems and planning solutions for industrial internet (IIoT).
80	R-DAS, s.r.o.	SK	Health, Energy, Payment and security solutions	Microelectronics			Research and development of smart electronic systems and their ASIC implementation, applicable in different industrial fields as well as other domains, e.g. quality of life, healthcare, wellness, etc.
81	REALTIME EMBEDDED AB	SE	IoT, Embedded systems	Product development and the construction and programming of advanced embedded systems.			
82	RECIF TECHNOLOGIES	FR	Semiconductor equipment manufacturer	Designs, manufactures, distributes and maintains robotic handling equipment for highly sensitive environments dedicated to the semiconductor industry.			
83	REDEN B.V.	NL	Transport, consumer, mechanical engineering	Virtual product testing.			Sectors: automotive, (consumer) electronics, aerospace and mechanical engineering.
84	ROBOTNIK AUTOMATION SLL	ES	Transport, Inspection & maintenance, Cleaning, security, agriculture, nuclear	Mobile service robotics. Logistics, Inspection & maintenance, Cleaning, Security & Defense, Agriculture, Nuclear, Urban transport.			Several fields (computers, manufacturing, industrial, telecommunications, mechanics, etc).
85	RoodMicrotec GmbH	DE	Semiconductors	Semiconductor company supplying products.			
86	ROVIMATICA S.L.	ES	Manufacturing, Transport	Industrial automation.			
87	Savvy Data Systems S.L.	ES	Manufacturing	Advanced monitoring and analytical solutions using Big Data for manufacturers of machine tools and for the processing industry.			

88	Saxony Media Solutions GmbH	DE	Transport, Manufacturing	Software and consulting (Business process optimization, Personal service plan creation, Production and logistics optimization).			
89	SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY BV	NL	IT	Information technology (IT) engineering			
90	SEARCH-LAB BIZTONSAGI ERTEKELO ELEMZO ES K	HU	Security	Security research and development			

91	Sencio BV	NL	Semiconductor	Packaging solutions for semiconductor devices, specifically (MEM's) sensors.			
92	SERVA TRANSPORT SYSTEMS GMBH	DE	Transport	Robotics (automated parking system).			
93	SILICON RADAR GMBH	DE	Manufacturing, Transport, Health	Designs and delivers Millimetre Wave Integrated Circuits (MMICs). Offer high frequency circuits for radar solutions, phased-array-systems and wireless communications.			Applications: Industrial Radars, Distance Control for UAVs, Terahertz imaging, Biosensing.
94	SIMPLAN AG	DE	Manufacturing, logistics	Simulation services and simulation software, e.g. Plant simulation			
95	SMARTESTING SOLUTIONS AND SERVICES SAS	FR	Model-based	Model-based testing consulting.			
96	SOFTEAM	FR	Software	Software vendor and engineering company.			
97	SOFTECO SISMAT SRL	IT	Energy & Utilities , Transport & Infrastructures, Industry, Finance	ICT Solutions: Mobile, Supervision & process Control.			
98	SOLMATES BV	NL	Semiconductor	Deposition equipment for next generation thin film applications. LED, MEMS, CMOS, PowerIC and OLEDs.			
99	SPACE SYSTEMS FINLAND OY	FI	Manufacturing, Health, Transport, Energy	Provides systems engineering and software development for leading customers in machinery, medical, space, defence, and nuclear industries.			
100	SPINVERSE INNOVATION MANAGEMENT OY	FI	Manufacturing, Energy (automation, chemicals, cleantech, electronics, energy, ICT, life)	Specialises in driving open innovation ecosystems, arranging funding and commercialising emerging technologies. sciences, machinery and mining.			
101	Statwolf Ltd.	IE	Marketing, manufacturing, sales, finance	Licenses Marketing Dashboards, and offers Advanced Data Science consulting. Predictive analytics, Event detection.	Statwolf platform - A smart, easy-touse online platform, it creates clear visualisations of data.		Statwolf dashboard integrates, visualises and analyses data from web traffic, social media, online advertising, SEO systems, CRM and more.

102	SYSGO AG	DE	Transport, Health, Manufacturing	Focuses on the basic software building blocks (e.g. operating systems) for embedded systems used in critical environments such as aeroplanes, medical instruments or industrial automation.		Real-time operating system PikeOS, which is certified to the highest safety and security standards, and the Embedded Linux distribution ELinOS.	
103	SYSTEMA SYSTEMENTWICKLUNG DIPL INF.MANFRED AUSTEN GMBH	DE	Manufacturing	Automation IT solutions	End-To-End Automation, Manufacturing IT and Enterprise Integration Solutions.		
104	TECHNIKON FORSCHUNGS- UND PLANUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH	AT	Service Provider	Provides research services and technology based consultancy to high-tech companies across Europe. It works on usable and cost effective hardware entangled security measures and develop individual security concepts and solutions.			Service Provider for Industry. Technikon's primary services are based on three pillars: 1. Planning, Management and Controlling, 2. Trusted Knowledge, 3. Security Engineering Services.
105	TECHNOLUTION BV	NL	Mobility, Energy, Industry, Public Safety & Security	Technology integrator, e.g. electronics, programmable logic, (embedded) software or a combination of these, using building blocks.			
106	Teco a.s.	CZ	Manufacturing	Industrial Automation, Intelligent Buildings, Smart Grid.			
107	TEKNE s.r.l.	IT	Transport, Manufacturing	Design and manufacture of electronic systems and electrical systems.			
108	TELLU AS	NO	Health	Innovate smart solutions for eHealth and personnel safety: Personnel safety, Welfare technology, Health care.	TelluCloud is a complete cloud platform for creating services and products with connectivity and Internet of Things functionality.		

109	TexEDA Design GmbH	DE	IC development	Offers a mature, customer-proven toolset called LayTools which is optimized for complex analog, RF and mixed signal IC development.			
110	TRIMEK SA	ES	Manufacturing	Supplies a wide range of products and solutions to improve the quality control and the in-line inspection processes.			Solutions: Measurement software, Non-contact in-line measurements, Large volumes inspection, Measurement rooms.
111	TTTECH COMPUTERTECHNIK AG	AT	Transport, Manufacturing, Energy	Dependable networking solutions based on timetriggered technology and modular safety platforms.			Deterministic Ethernet, Time-Triggered Protocol (TTP), Guarantee of Service for Real-Time IoT, Advanced Driver Assistance Systems.
112	TWT GMBH SCIENCE & INNOVATION	DE	Transport, Health, Energy	Engineering, IT, and consulting			
113	ULMA EMBEDDED SOLUTIONS S COOP	ES	Transport, Energy, Health, Industrial	Embedded systems engineering services.		Work with standards such as, EN 50155, IEC 62304, EN 50128, ISO 26262, IEC 60730, EN 60601, UL 61010, ISO 13849, IEC 61508, etc.	Offer specialized engineering services along the whole electronic product lifecycle, from the concept to manufacturing and maintenance, including design, development and test phases.

114	VERHAERT NEW PRODUCTS & SERVICES NV	BE	Transport, Health, Security, Connect, Consumer, Industry, Technology transfer	Complete innovation life cycle from strategy over development towards industrial and commercial launch.			
115	VI-grade Srl	IT	Transport	Software simulation products and engineering services.			
116	X-CELEPRINT LTD	IE	Flexible electronics, RFIDs, Microscale ICs for the Internet-of-Things, LEDs and lasers, Sensors, etc.	Advanced Micro-Transfer-Printing Technology Solutions.			
117	XenomatiX	BE	Transport	Automotive vision solutions. 360° precise and high resolution sensing under all light and weather conditions and at any driving speed.			
118	XENON AUTOMATISIERUNGSTECHNIK GMBH	DE	Transport, Energy, Health, Electronics	Develops and manufactures machines and plants for the automation of production processes.			
119	Xetal nv	BE	Health, People localisation	Indoor people localisation technology e.g. Patient Bed Monitoring, personalized care services, Smart Senior Care, Real-Time Smart Vision systems.			
120	XMOD TECHNOLOGIES	FR	Semiconductor	Provides services and software to the semiconductor industry.			
121	ZS-HANDLING GMBH	DE	Energy, Semiconductor, Glass	Non-contact handling technologies for photovoltaic, semiconductor and glass industries. Technology: ultrasound-air-bearing.			

